

Magnetic iron oxide nanoparticles have potential on gene therapy effectiveness and biocompatibility

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Abstract- Recent breakthroughs in employing magnetic iron oxide nanoparticles (IONPs) to improve gene transmission to stem cells are outlined in this study, which highlights IONPs' unique properties as biocompatible metal-based gene delivery vectors. The physicochemical characteristics of IONPs, as discussed in this study, have a major effect on gene transmission effectiveness and biocompatibility with stem cells. Regulated syntheses of homogeneous IONPs are preferable for successful, reproducible gene delivery. In addition, synthesizing or assembling IONPs with higher ARs can boost cell absorption, enhancing the effectiveness of gene transmission to stem cells. In addition, magnetofection technology has a substantial influence on stem cell gene transmission. An unoptimized transfection approach resulted in severe cytotoxicity and a significant reduction in levels of gene expression. Gene delivery using IONPs and external magnetic force, on the other hand, has demonstrated excellent results in overcoming serum interference and boosting target gene transmission to 3D cell cultures. Notably, serum-resistant and 3D gene transfer are beneficial for maintaining stem cell survival and stem after magnetofection. However, considerable challenges remain in the way IONP-assisted gene trafficking to stem cells, including the unknown bioeffects of IONPs on stem cell behavior and the large-scale fabrication of controlled size and shape monodispersed IONPs. Used at appropriate concentrations for gene delivery, IONPs exhibit no deleterious influence on stem cell survival, proliferation, and differentiation capacity. However, the dose-dependent toxicity of IONPs and the potential hazards associated with using transfection agents such as PEI require extra attention. Moreover, the potential bio-influences of IONPs and ionized ions on stem cell biological behaviors should be thoroughly examined and studies of new undiscovered bio-effects should continue. Meanwhile, another issue worth addressing for the real use of IONPs as a powerful and omnipresent platform tool to transport target genes to stem cells for medicinal reasons is the large-scale synthesis of homogeneous IONPs with low interbatch variations. IONPs have shown their extraordinary ability to increase the effectiveness of gene transport to stem cells, making them superior to other gene delivery techniques in terms of multifunctional stem cell engineering, paired with their high biocompatibility and promising functionality. However, the challenges of using IONPs to deliver genes to stem cells involve chemistry, physics, material science, pharmaceuticals, and cell biology and require more multidisciplinary collaborations to achieve breakthroughs and translate this promising stem cell gene delivery strategy into medical practice

I. INTRODUCTION

Due to their ability to develop into specialized cells or create numerous bioactive compounds, such as cytokines and growth factors, stem cells have proved their tremendous promise in regenerative medicine, gene therapy, immunotherapy, and other disease therapies throughout the last decades. (1) However, the therapeutic benefits of stem cells in real-world applications are frequently hampered owing to unfavorable disease microenvironments. To increase the efficacy of stem-cell-based therapeutics, further genetic alterations of stem cells are urgently needed. Neural stem cells (NSCs), for example, have neuroprotective properties, but their effectiveness is restricted after a stroke due to the hostile brain environment. (2) It exhibited significantly excellent functional recovery of stroke mice employing genetic engineering of NSCs to overexpress brain-derived neurotrophic factor when compared to the therapy utilizing original NSCs. (3) Furthermore, certain genetic changes in stem cells may provide skills that confer unique roles on previously undeveloped traits. For example, Liu L et al. used gene transduction using the mechanosensitive promoter to create mechanoresponsive mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs) that could be preferentially home to cancer metastases. (4) More recently, it was discovered that certain stem cells, such as MSCs and NSCs, have the unique capacity of homing to wounded tissues, allowing them to be used as cellular carriers for the targeted delivery of drugs/genes to diseased tissues. (5) The high loading of therapeutic genes without compromising the bio-behavior of stem cells is a requirement of this design, making efficient and biocompatible gene transport to stem cells crucial. We previously used MSCs as tumor-targeting vehicles to load suicide genes (e.g., herpes simplex virus thymidine kinase, HSV-TK) by gene transfection, revealing HSV-TK expression to be quite high. Furthermore, in the absence of the prodrug, the suicide gene expression had no effect on MSC proliferation or migration. The use of transfected MSCs as gene vehicles for tumor-targeting treatment resulted in robust selective tumor elimination via bystander effects in the presence of the prodrug, demonstrating the potential of

MSCs as gene vehicles for tumor-targeting therapy. (6)

Viruses are currently the most widely used vectors for delivering target genes to stem cells, but several negative side effects, such as potential cytotoxicity, insertional mutagenesis, and immunogenicity, have raised concerns about clinical applications and hampered routine laboratory applications in basic research. (7) Some insect DNA viruses, such as baculoviral vectors, were later designed to bypass these safety concerns. (8) However, because of the poor DNA carrying capacity, production and packaging issues, and expensive prices, this technique is currently limited. (7) Meanwhile, a non-viral method based on polymers, liposomes, and micelles has piqued attention due to its benefits of non-insertional gene transfection and minimal immune reaction, as well as comparatively inexpensive costs for large-scale manufacturing. (5, 6, 9) However, their gene expression levels, particularly in stem cells, need to be enhanced. (6), (9) Biocompatible inorganic nanomaterials, such as gold nanoparticles, (10), magnetic iron oxide nanoparticles (IONPs), (11), and quantum dots, are a rapidly growing field in gene delivery. They are simpler to manage because of their tiny size and maintain more consistency than organic nanoparticles, allowing for better penetration of cell membranes with loaded genes. (12)

Furthermore, their tiny size results in a high surface area-to-volume ratio, resulting in a dense gene loading. (9 and 13) Because of these advantages, as well as other characteristics such as extensive functionality, storage durability, and ease of large-scale manufacturing, biocompatible inorganic nanoparticles appear to have the potential to improve gene delivery efficiency. Magnetic IONPs, such as magnetite and maghemite, in particular, have demonstrated significant potential for enhancing gene transport efficiency. IONPs have a substantial advantage over other non-magnetic nanomaterials in that they are magnetic, allowing magnetic force to be used to accelerate and enhance the deposition of IONPs and loaded genes on cell membranes. Furthermore, IONPs have a comparative advantage over other magnetic inorganic nanoparticles in terms of being benign, non-toxic, and physiologically tolerable. (14) As a result, IONPs are particularly appealing as a potent nanotool for boosting gene transport to stem cells due to their effective gene transport capabilities and great biocompatibility.

Stem cells, on the other hand, are very sensitive to the gene transfection environment and have a low activity in the absorption of foreign materials, making the physicochemical features of IONPs and the transfection environment crucial for both gene delivery efficiency and cytotoxicity. As a result, understanding how these parameters affect the whole trip of IONPs into stem cells and affect stem cell biologic behaviors would be useful in guiding the design of biocompatible IONPs and the construction of IONP-assisted gene delivery systems. For that purpose, we present a general overview of the guiding principles governing the effects of IONPs' physicochemical qualities on stem cells, as well as a summary of the critical effects imposed by the transfection method on the effectiveness of IONPs-assisted gene delivery. Moreover, some key problems, such as the bioeffects of IONPs on stem cell biologic behaviors and the large-scale synthesis of uniform IONPs, were addressed, which may obstruct the practical application of IONPs for gene delivery to stem cells.

II. GENE DELIVERY TO STEM CELLS USING IONPS

Several key hurdles will obstruct the delivery of genes to the interior of target cells during the journey: i) cellular absorption across cell membranes; ii) endosomal escape; iii) intracellular transport and stability of genes; iv) nuclear entrance of genes (DNA). (7, 12, 15) Formalized paraphrase to overcome the aforementioned obstacles, sophisticated gene delivery vectors are necessary. Plank and Mah were among the first to use IONPs as a potent adjuvant for gene delivery vectors to improve gene transduction or transfection effectiveness. (16) Subsequently, significant progress was achieved in this sector, and this IONPs-based method was used in gene delivery to stem cells for several years after its first publication. (17) Several commercial magnetofection reagents are currently available for gene transfection of embryonic stem cells (ESCs) and neural stem cells (NSCs), such as PolyMAG from Chemicell GmbH and NeuroMag from Oz Biosciences. (17, 18)

The primary contribution of magnetic IONPs to the gene delivery process is the concentration of a large number of genes that stick to cell membranes within minutes with the help of an external magnetic field. (15) The enhanced internalization of delivered genes as a result of the rapid deposition of IONPs and loaded genes on the cell surface improves gene delivery efficiency. (19) Because of this mechanical process, IONPs may be used to transfer genes to a variety of stem/precursor cells, including MSCs, NSCs, ESCs, and induced pluripotent stem cells. Notably, despite the fact that IONPs enhance gene internalization over time, they have no effect on cellular absorption or subsequent nuclear targeting. Due to the high gene density in the cytoplasm, the rapid and enhanced shuttling of genes into the cytoplasm enhances the risk of passive nuclear translocation and infiltration in a dose-dependent way. (11, 15, 21, and 22) Furthermore, stem cells are more sensitive to external treatments and have slower ex vivo proliferation than most other cell types, implying poor internalization of gene complexes and fewer opportunities to harness the M phase for nuclear entry, making them "difficult-to-transfect cells" for most non-viral gene delivery methods. (15 and 22) According to the aforementioned research, IONPs have the potential to bypass cell membrane barriers, allowing more loaded genes to reach the cytoplasm in a very short period, enhancing passive nuclear entrance, and boosting the possibility of benefiting from mitotic effects. Furthermore, the use of IONPs for fast gene delivery reduces the negative effects associated with long-term gene transfer. (14, 15, 23) A particular combination of cationic polymer/gene complexes with IONPs has also been reported to modify the intracellular distribution of the cationic polymer and increase gene release following endosomal escape, therefore improving gene transfection efficiency and lowering cytotoxicity. (15) When compared to cationic polymers alone, these traits highlight the advantages of using cationic polymer-coated IONPs for gene transport to stem cells. In addition, some recent studies have shown that IONPs have unique bioeffects on stem cell biologic behaviors following internalization, such as enhancing MSC homing capability to wounded tissues by actively up-regulating homing-related CXC

chemokine receptor 4 (CXCR4) expression. (21, 24)

Magnetic IONPs have enormous potential to solve the current challenges of efficient biocompatible gene delivery to stem cells, thanks to their apparent advantages in improving gene delivery efficiency to diverse stem cells, as well as their short transfection procedures, excellent biocompatibility, and some favorable bioeffects. Magnetic IONPs have also been described as promising MRI contrast agents for stem cell tracking, (37), demonstrating their multi-functionality in labeling and visualizing transfected stem cells. As a result of the foregoing characteristics, magnetic IONPs have a distinct advantage over conventional nanomaterials in terms of gene transport to stem cells. The next section discusses the benefits, processes, and problems of employing IONPs for gene delivery to stem cells, as well as the physicochemical features of IONPs and gene transfection methods.

Effects of IONP Physicochemical Properties

The magnetic IONPs, which can concentrate the given genes on the surface of target cells within minutes with the help of an external magnetic field, are often credited for the improved gene delivery efficiency achieved by utilizing IONPs. (15) The greater internalization of transmitted genes due to the faster deposition of IONPs on the cell surface improves gene delivery efficiency. (19)

According to these studies, magnetic IONPs' capacity to expedite the deposition of loaded genes on the surface of target cells is crucial for gene delivery effectiveness, which is mostly determined by the physicochemical features of the IONPs utilized. As a result, the concepts and impacts of physicochemical features such as particle size, shape, composition, homogeneity, assembly strategy, and surface modification on gene transport to stem cells are first discussed.

3.1 Particle Dimensions

The size of nanoparticles has a significant impact on their cellular absorption, transport, and accumulation, and hence on their future gene delivery efficiency. (38) Various sized nanoparticles have different contact areas and patterns with target cells, which is linked to the membrane wrapping process and influences cellular absorption efficiency, routes, and nanoparticle kinetics. (38 and 39) As a result, proper particle size optimization is crucial for improving cellular absorption efficiency. The optimal particle size for cellular uptake was reported to be between 50 and 100 nm. (40, 39) Huang J et al. studied the cellular absorption of IONPs with various particle sizes (30-120 nm), finding that the highest cellular uptake occurred at around 100 nm. (41) One proposed reason was that this size had an optimum nanointerface between nanoparticles and cell membranes, resulting in significant nanoparticle-cell interactions by binding with cluster receptors on cell membranes, and eventually generating successful nanoparticle cellular uptake. (40 and 42) When compared to their bigger counterparts, smaller nanoparticles (50 nm) showed less nanointerface between nanoparticles and cell membranes. (43) Due to slower receptor diffusion, larger nanoparticles typically acted much slower and had poorer cellular uptake, resulting in a longer wrapping time. (44) Jo J et al. gave an example in which they made IONPs of various sizes by altering the molar ratio of the pullulan hydroxyl group to ferric ions during the mixing process. The largest quantity of intracellular iron was found in the size range of 50–100 nm, but IONP internalization was significantly decreased when the size was more than 100 nm. (45)

Furthermore, particle size was shown to have a significant influence on the magnetic characteristics of IONPs. Magnetite found in nature has a ferrimagnetic characteristic and a Curie temperature (858 K). The maximum coercivity was attained by shrinking magnetite to a nano-size of less than 100 nm. The IONPs exhibited superparamagnetic properties when the particle size was smaller than 20 nm. (14) The size-dependent magnetization of IONPs influenced their sedimentation velocity on cell surfaces, which was influenced by an external magnetic field. IONPs with a bigger size had higher saturation magnetization values and heavier weight in most cases (45, 46), suggesting a faster sedimentation of the target cell over time owing to the attraction of both external magnetic force and gravity. (47) On the other hand, while high magnetization of IONPs usually benefits from a strong response to external magnetic force, over-high magnetization may lead to large aggregates due to the strong magnetic attraction between IONPs, (48), which has negative effects on cellular uptake and results in poor colloidal stability of IONPs-associated gene complexes (also known as magnetoparticles). As a result, most recent investigations have used superparamagnetic IONPs (SPIONs or SPIOs) as the magnetic core, often in the 10–20 nm range. When the external magnetic force was removed, these SPIONs showed no magnetism, allowing them to take advantage of colloidal stability.

Overall, IONP size had a significant impact on gene transport effectiveness by influencing nanoparticle-cell membrane contacts and magnetic characteristics, which influenced sedimentation velocity and the subsequent cellular internalization process and endocytosis pathways of magnetic gene complexes. To establish a superior compromise of the nanointerface with cluster receptors on cell membranes, the magnetic response of IONPs to external magnetic force, and the colloidal stability of the magnetoplexes, the size of IONPs should first be addressed.

3.2 Particle Shape

The form of the particle has a significant influence on cellular absorption, mostly through changing the aspect ratios (ARs). (49) Larger AR nanoparticles have more contact with cell membrane receptors, indicating a substantial degree of cellular absorption and fast internalization. (49) Surprisingly, despite the fact that most nanoparticles reported in the literature were spherical in shape, they had low ARs (ARs = 1), resulting in minimal interaction with cell membrane receptors and the lowest cellular uptake when compared to short nanorods (ARs = 2) or

long nanorods (ARs = 4). (49) These findings suggested that nanoparticle shape is important in cellular absorption processes, which was later verified by Agarwal R H et al. Because of the high ARs, their research revealed that nanodiscs were more successful at internalization than nanorods. (50)

The Xu FJ group gave more evidence supporting the impact of particle shape. They looked at the gene transport effectiveness of five distinct morphologies of gold nanoparticles (gold nanospheres, gold nano-octahedra, arrow-headed gold nanorods, and gold nanorods with varying ARs) and found that particle shape has a substantial influence on gene transport effectiveness. Notably, their research revealed that larger ARs aided cellular absorption, but that this did not imply that larger ARs were better. Nanorods with shorter ARs (39 nm in length) performed better in endocytosis and had higher gene transport efficiency than those with longer ARs (105 nm in length). (51) Better AR nanoparticles, such as rod-like nanoparticles, have higher cellular absorption than lower AR nanoparticles, such as spherical nanoparticles, in most circumstances, suggesting a unique path for improving gene delivery effectiveness by optimizing particle form.

Furthermore, Herd H et al. demonstrated that the geometrical forms of nanoparticles can influence cellular endocytic pathways. Because of their greater dimensions, spherical silica nanoparticles were mostly taken up by clathrin-mediated endocytosis, whereas cylindrical and worm-shaped nanoparticles were mostly taken up by macropinocytosis or phagocytic processes. The cellular absorption of cylindrical and worm-shaped particles was greater than that of spheres due to various endocytotic routes. (53) This discovery showed that the structure of nanoparticles can influence their cellular absorption method, opening up a new way to improve gene delivery efficiency by modifying particle form.

Furthermore, through the surface anisotropy term, the particle shape plays a critical role in defining the magnetic characteristics of IONPs. (45 and 46) Because of the differing anisotropy constants produced by the difference in surface anisotropic terms, IONPs in a cubic spinel structure displayed a greater magnetic susceptibility than their counterparts in a spherical spinel structure. (54) Our recent research also found that hysteresis cycle behavior differed significantly across magnetite nanoparticles of comparable particle sizes but different particle shapes, with the nanocubes having a substantially greater magnetic saturation than the nanospheres. (21) Furthermore, when compared to various particle forms such as pseudocubes and peanuts, Li M et al. discovered that ellipsoid-shaped particles had the biggest magnetic moment. (55) Spherical IONPs had the lowest magnetic susceptibility when compared to other usual morphologies such as cubes, plates, tetrahedrons, rhombohedra, and octapods, similar to the prior findings involving ARs. (56) To summarize, the particle form has key features that influence cellular absorption and reactivity to magnetic fields, hence determining gene transport efficiency. In the ARs and surface anisotropy, traditional spherical particles failed to show any benefit. As a result, additional particle shape improvements for more effective gene delivery will be a viable research field.

3.3 Particle Structure

The magnetic characteristics of IONPs are mostly determined by their composition. Because of the varied redox states, IONPs with distinct crystalline phases, such as magnetite (Fe_3O_4), maghemite ($-\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$), and hematite ($-\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$), have distinct magnetic characteristics. (57) Because of their strong magnetism, simplicity of manufacture, and outstanding biocompatibility, Fe_3O_4 -containing nanoparticles are the most extensively used magnetic nanoparticles for gene transfer. (58) In a dose-dependent way, Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles promote autophagic cell death more than maghemite in murine alveolar macrophage cells, according to a recent study. The breakdown of Fe_3O_4 in endo/lysosomes may result in free Fe^{2+} , which then catalyzes Fenton-type reactions, resulting in harmful radicals. (59) While $-\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ has been shown to be more stable in endo/lysosomes than Fe_3O_4 , producing less free Fe^{2+} . (60) As a result of its minimal cytotoxicity to stem cells, maghemite nanoparticles have recently been produced for gene transfer. Magro M et al., for example, employed surface active maghemite nanoparticles to successfully transfer pDNA to MSCs. (34) Despite the fact that the oxidation state of iron has an effect on biocompatibility, the concentration of IONPs is the most important component in determining cytotoxicity. IONPs (Fe_3O_4 and Fe_2O_3) at concentrations of less than 100 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ are usually regarded as non-cytotoxic. (60)

Several studies, on the other hand, have replaced Fe^{2+} ions with other divalent transition metal ions, such as Zn^{2+} , in order to achieve rapid sedimentation of the magnetoplexes with the help of external magnetic force, because only Fe^{2+} ions in the octahedral sites of magnetite contribute to the net magnetic moment. (11, 62) Zinc ferrite (ZnFe_2O_4) nanoparticles have a substantially greater magnetic susceptibility than magnetite or maghemite nanoparticles when partial ferrous ions are replaced by zinc ions. (62) ZnFe_2O_4 nanoparticles also exhibit dose-dependent cytotoxicity toward stem cells, similar to Fe_3O_4 or $-\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ nanoparticles. At low concentrations of ZnFe_2O_4 nanoparticles, for example, essentially no dangerous effects were found on MSCs (e.g., 0.11 μM). (63) As a result, ZnFe_2O_4 nanoparticles' increased magnetic susceptibility assists in achieving the same magnetic performance as magnetite and maghemite at considerably lower concentrations, minimizing the risk of cytotoxicity. (62) Shah B et al., for example, produced a magnetic core-shell nanoparticle using ZnFe_2O_4 as the magnetic core, demonstrating the potential for effective siRNA delivery to NSCs with little cytotoxicity. (11) The surface coating and cell types, however, have an impact on the biocompatibility of ZnFe_2O_4 nanoparticles. According to the findings, silica-coated cobalt zinc ferrite nanoparticles inhibited the proliferation of human-induced pluripotent stem cell-derived neural precursors (hiPSC-NPs), but poly-L-lysine-coated maghemite had no such effects. (64)

Under normal circumstances, zinc ferrite nanoparticles have a greater potential for efficient and biocompatible gene transfer to stem cells, based on magnetic properties and safety hazards. Maghemite nanoparticles, on the other hand, have a lower probability of producing harmful radicals than magnetite nanoparticles. (59) On the other hand, Fe₃O₄ has various advantages, including simpler large-scale synthesis and faster breakdown in a lysosome-mimicking environment. (58) Future research concentrating on this feature will be fascinating and useful in guiding the development of IONPs for gene delivery.

3.4 Nanoparticle Uniformity

So far, we've spoken about how particle size, shape, and content have a big impact on gene delivery efficiency. Notably, all of the above arguments are dependent on nanoparticle homogeneity, which has a significant impact on the magnetic properties and cellular absorption of IONPs, (43, 65), and hence influences the efficiency of gene delivery. Low homogeneity makes it difficult to maintain nanoparticle consistency in ideal settings, resulting in poor gene expression level repeatability. Furthermore, poor uniformity may have an adverse effect on optimum gene delivery efficiency, primarily through the influence on cellular uptake efficiency. It is hypothesized that IONPs with a narrow size range, such as uniform 50 nm, will demonstrate a faster uptake than IONPs with a broader size range, such as 50–200 nm. (65) Feridex, a dextran-coated SPION, has been found to be limited in its use in gene transfer to stem cells, in part due to its low consistency. (66) The size and form of nanoparticles can also impact how they interact with cells. (15) As a result, a wide range of nanoparticle sizes can cause a variety of interactions, raising the possibility of unintended negative consequences such as the development of persistent inflammatory cascades and size-dependent cell damage. (53, 67) Furthermore, as previously stated, the size and form of IONPs have a significant influence on their magnetic properties. Thus, uniform IONPs are widely chosen for optimizing the required magnetic susceptibility by adjusting nanoparticle size and shape in order to accomplish effective gene delivery. (14) The tremendous benefits of ultra-uniform IONPs were first revealed in investigations of IONPs used as MRI contrast agents. (54, 68) Highly uniform IONPs with small size variation have recently demonstrated their unique advantages in effective and low-toxic gene delivery to MSCs. 11 and 29

Several chemosynthesis approaches have been developed recently to permit the high homogeneity of IONPs, which we have discussed in detail.

Some of these processes include thermal decomposition (69), sol-gel (70), and hydrothermal reaction.(71) Heyon T et al. also published a heat-up approach for large-scale synthesis of very uniform-sized and -shaped maghemite nanoparticles without a size-selection step, which will be explored in the next sections.

Finally, the homogeneity of IONPs requires special attention in gene delivery since it is critical for maintaining appropriate physicochemical qualities for maximum gene delivery effectiveness. Furthermore, utilizing IONPs with a small size or shape variation enables further reduction of size- and shape-dependent cytotoxicity by physicochemical parameter optimization, avoiding the inadvertent dangers associated with wider fluctuations.

3.5 Surface Modification

Surface modification of bare IONPs confers colloidal stability, biocompatibility, and gene binding capacity, all of which are required for effective gene delivery applications. In aqueous conditions, the protonation nature of iron atoms on the surface of IONPs contributes to the creation of hydroxyl groups on the surface, allowing for a simple interaction with acids and bases for additional surface functionalization. (14) IONPs have been coated with a variety of polymers, monomers, and inorganic compounds to produce effective gene delivery.

Surface modification was required for IONPs produced utilizing nonhydrolytic synthetic techniques, such as thermal breakdown or hydrothermal reaction, in order to permit the hydrophobic characteristic and increase aquatic stability. Additionally, these surface coating layers serve as a substrate for IONP functionalization. (72) Furthermore, the surface properties of IONPs have a direct influence on cellular uptake behavior. (73) The cellular absorption of SPIONs coated with organosilica (SiO₂) was greater than that of SPIONs coated with dextran or polyethylene glycol. (74) Zhu XM et al. examined the cellular absorption of naked SPIONs from SPIONs coated with aminosilane (SiO₂-NH₂), SiO₂, or dextran in another investigation. (75) Because of their ease of aggregation in the cultural media, bare SPIONs had the lowest cellular absorption by mouse MSCs. The nanoparticle aggregation was inhibited by a surface coating of SiO₂-NH₂, SiO₂, and dextran, resulting in increased cellular absorption. Furthermore, SPION@SiO₂-NH₂ had a larger cellular uptake than SPION@SiO₂, owing to the former's positive charge, which made cellular internalization easier than the latter. Furthermore, when compared to SPION@SiO₂, the dextran-coated SPIONs' poor fluid-phase endocytosis route resulted in less adequate cellular uptake. These examples demonstrate the significance of surface modification in affecting IONP cellular absorption and, as a result, gene delivery efficiency.

Furthermore, in aqueous settings, the hydroxyl groups on the surface of bare IONPs result in a negatively charged particle surface. (14, 76) As a result, positive IONP surface alterations are particularly important for the subsequent binding of negatively charged genes. Furthermore, cationic nanoparticles absorb more efficiently into cells than anionic and electroneutral counterparts.(14, 77) This is due to the presence of large negatively charged domains in cell membranes, which reject anionic nanoparticles while preferring cationic nanoparticles. (78) Furthermore, the cationic surface may cause nanoparticle internalization via clathrin-mediated endocytosis, resulting in rapid cellular uptake

and, as a result, effective gene delivery. Because of their branching internal structure and the abundance of surface primary amines that may readily bind and condense genes, polyethylenimine (PEI) is the most often used cationic polymer for the cationization of IONPs. (80) PEI also shows the potential to disrupt the endosomal membrane, allowing DNA to escape from endosomes while also protecting it from destruction, a phenomenon known as the "proton sponge effect." (81)

The PEI modification, in which IONPs were produced in the PEI solution, was employed in the first reported applications of IONPs-assisted gene transport. (16, 82) The benefits of covalent coupling of PEI with IONPs to improve gene transport efficiency were also described by Namgung R et al. PEI with a low molecular weight (MW 1.8K) has a lower transfection ability than PEI with a high molecular weight (MW 1.8K) (MW 25K). Covalent conjugation of 1.8K-PEI on SPIONs, on the other hand, exhibited gene transport efficiency equivalent to 2.5K-PEI coating while also demonstrating greater cell survival than 2.5K-PEI coating. (58) Aside from the cationic polymer coating, various polysaccharides, such as dextran, (83), pullulan, (11), chitosan, (84), and heparin (85), have been used to coat IONPs for gene delivery, because these polysaccharides could readily bind to receptors on stem cells and increase cellular uptake.

In addition to organic compounds, biocompatible inorganic materials such as gold and silica have been described as surface coatings. These inorganic materials are commonly coated as a shell layer on IONPs to protect the iron oxide cores from oxidation and reactive species while also allowing for easy surface modification for multifunctional medicinal applications. Gold shells are a popular choice because they are biocompatible, inert, and easy to modify using thiol-containing ligands. (86) The gold shell layer also allows the IONPs to absorb near-infrared (NIR) light and scatter photons. (88) Shah B et al., for example, developed a core-shell structure nanoparticle of ZnFe₂O₄@Au with additional cationization using a cationic polyamine dendrimer, demonstrating a strong capacity to transport siRNA to NSCs as well as the ability to image the nanoparticles in NSCs using dark-field light scattering. (11) Furthermore, due to its high biocompatibility and ease of decorating on IONPs using either the Stöber method or the reverse microemulsion methodology, silica is another extensively utilized inorganic material for coating IONPs. (14, 89) Mykhaylyk O et al., for example, used PEI coated silica-IONPs to increase viral gene delivery efficiency. (90) However, to the best of our knowledge, silica-IONPs have only been used for gene transport to stem cells in a few cases.

3.6 Assembling Techniques

3.6.1 Magnetic Core-Nanoparticle Assembly in One Dimension

As previously stated, nanoparticle ARs have a significant influence on cellular internalization and, consequently, gene transport efficiency. As a result, in addition to the controlled synthesis of nanoparticles in bigger AR shapes, nanoparticle assembly of 1D nanostructures is another possible alternative. The assemblage of spherical nanoparticles into 1D nanostructures, for example, increases their ARs, indicating improved cellular absorption. (53, 91) Even in the absence of external magnetic fields, Wang R et al. joined two spherical IONPs by covering them with silica to construct permanent 1D peapod-like magnetic nanoparticles (Fe₃O₄@SiO₂). These 1D peapod-like magnetic nanoparticles were subsequently linked with ethanolamine-functionalized poly (glycidyl methacrylate), demonstrating a much greater gene transport efficiency than spherical nanoparticles. (92)

Similarly, in prior research, we used permanent magnetic dipole interactions between FIONs to build uniform ferrimagnetic iron oxide nanocubes (FIONs) into 1D nanochains (MFIONs). (21) These 1D nanochains had a substantially wider contact area with the MSC membrane than their spherical counterparts, allowing for easier cellular uptake and more effective gene transport. These studies suggest that assembling single nanoparticles into 1D nanostructures might improve gene delivery by bypassing the time-consuming manufacturing required to accurately regulate particle shape and allowing the ARs to be modified during the construction process for optimal cellular absorption.

3.6.2 Magnetoplex

Notably, magnetoplex assembly procedures have a significant impact on cellular uptake and endosomal escape rates, hence affecting the effectiveness of gene delivery. Arsianti et al. first revealed this important result in a study in which iron oxide magnetic nanoparticles (MNP) were combined with DNA and PEI in four distinct orders. The order in which these triplexes were assembled had a major influence on gene expression levels. (47) The argument is that the magnetoplexes' size and surface charge are determined by the assembly order, which affects their cellular uptake, endosomal escape, and intracellular localisation. Other assembly techniques were more or less restricted by endosomal escape rates; the assembly of PEI/DNA complexes on the outside of MNP demonstrated the greatest cellular uptake and facilitated DNA localization in the nucleus; other assembly strategies were more or less limited by endosomal escape rates. (47, 93) Aside from improved gene delivery, magnetoplex assembly procedures also resulted in increased gene release and lower cytotoxicity. In comparison to PEI/DNA complexes, the strong binding of IONPs with PEI/DNA complexes prevented PEI from entering the nucleus and facilitated the effective release of DNA, indicating decreased cytotoxicity and more effective gene delivery. (15, 94)

These examples demonstrate that magnetoplex assembly strategies have important effects on cellular uptake, as well as important influences on the subsequent endo/lysosomal escape process, intracellular gene release, and nuclear localization, putting the elegant assembly of magnetoplexes in the same category as the physiochemical properties of IONPs for gene delivery.

III. TRANSFECTION SYSTEM CONSEQUENCES

Despite the fact that IONPs' physicochemical properties are important in cellular uptake and subsequent gene delivery, transfection systems, such as magnetic fields, transfection procedures, and magnetofection conditions, have a significant impact on the performance and biocompatibility of IONPs in stem cell gene delivery. As a result, optimizing the transfection mechanism is critical for effective and biocompatible gene delivery to stem cells. The primary effects of the transfection system on the performance of IONPs-assisted gene delivery have been outlined in this paper from two perspectives: i) The effects of applied magnetic fields; ii) The effects of magnetofection situations

4.1 External Magnetic Fields

4.1.1 Magnetic Field Intensity

As previously stated, the magnetic attraction caused by external magnetic fields causes a high number of IONPs and loaded genes to travel rapidly toward the surface of target cells, which is the fundamental determinant of enhanced gene delivery. According to Equation (1), which displays the principal influences of the magnetic field density (B) on the magnetic force (F_{mag}) to attract IONPs, a greater external magnetic field with a higher intensity favors a faster sedimentation of the magnetoplexes owing to a stronger magnetic force on magnetic IONPs: (95) Nonetheless, the increased magnetic force will cause IONPs to aggregate excessively, compromising their stability and perhaps causing cytotoxicity. As a result, only a correct external magnetic force aids in improving gene transport efficiency, whereas an unoptimized magnetic force may harm stem cells. For example, Lee CH et al., the first to disclose the use of magnetic fields and IONPs to improve gene delivery efficiency to ESCs, said that using the right magnetic field intensity and exposure period decreased the harmful effects of magnetofection processes on stem cells. (17) Furthermore, Son S et al. discovered that an inappropriate magnetic field might cause MSC mortality and poor gene expression by causing the magnetoplexes to have an excessively high cellular absorption rate and disrupting the cell membranes. (22) Furthermore, we found that the strength of the external magnetic field had an effect on gene delivery effectiveness, with either a relatively mild (0.19 T) or an overly high (0.5 T) magnetic field limiting gene transport efficiency of MSCs in our prior work. (11)

4.1.2 Magnetic Fields That Aren't Static

Several studies have recently attempted to use a non-static magnetic field instead of a static magnetic field for gene delivery, owing to the fact that the external magnetic field has a significant influence on gene delivery efficiency. Kamau et al. made the first effort, employing a low-frequency pulsed magnetic field to achieve significantly greater gene delivery efficiency than a permanent magnet for both tiny (50 nm) and big (200–250 nm) SPIONs. (96) This approach of applying a pulsed magnetic field has proved very successful for a variety of primary cells. (97) Jenkins SI et al. employed a high-gradient NdFeB oscillating array to transport genes to oligodendrocyte precursor cells, revealing that the oscillating magnetic fields generated greater gene expression than the static equivalent. They also demonstrated the effects of oscillating magnetic field frequency on gene delivery effectiveness, finding that 4 Hz oscillating magnetic fields produced better gene expression than 1 Hz oscillating magnetic fields. (26) Adams CF et al. also used oscillating magnetic fields for gene transfection of NSCs, yielding considerably greater gene expression levels than when static magnetic fields were used. They also found that raising the frequency of oscillating magnetic fields to 5 Hz lowered transfection effectiveness as compared to 4 Hz. (18)

Their findings suggest that using optimum oscillating magnetic fields to boost the gene transport capabilities of IONPs might be a viable approach. Commercially available oscillating magnetic fields at low frequency (1–5 Hz) include NanoTherics (nanoTherics Ltd, UK), which is based on Jon Dobson's original concept. (95) Furthermore, Oral O et al. recently developed a unique oscillating magnetic system that allows for changing magnet turn rates and magnetic field directions, demonstrating the potential for IONPs-assisted gene transport. (98) Despite the fact that oscillating magnetic fields have been successful in gene transfer, the precise process is yet unknown. Alternating magnetic fields, according to Plank C et al., convey mechanical stresses to cell membranes via magnetic particles attached to cell surfaces, boosting cellular absorption. (15)

4.1.3 Gene Delivery Without a Magnetic Field

Despite the fact that the rapid sedimentation of IONPs on cell membranes caused by external magnetic fields is the primary contributor to improved gene delivery, the magnetic forces generated by external magnetic fields also have the potential to affect cell behavior and cell signaling via the bounded IONPs on cell membranes.

(99) As a result, gene delivery utilizing IONPs without the usage of external magnetic fields has lately garnered a lot of traction in order to prevent potential interferences induced by external magnetic forces on stem cells. Furthermore, this technique does not involve the optimization of external magnetic field strengths, which is advantageous for low-cost practical applications. For example, we created FIONs-associated gene complexes that self-assembled into 1D nanochains with high ARs in an aqueous environment, allowing us to transport genes to MSCs efficiently and safely without the need for external magnetic fields. (21) Lu L et al. also used a cationic polymersome to include SPIONs for effective siRNA delivery to NSCs, eliminating the need for external magnetic fields. The reasoning for this design is based on the structural similarities of nanoscale polymersomes to physiological vesicles, allowing for easier cellular absorption. (100) These examples suggest that by using elegant IONP structure designs or surface changes, magnetic field-independent gene delivery may be possible.

4.2 Time for exposure and incubation

One of the most important benefits of IONPs-assisted gene transport is that it speeds up the process. Cells are subjected to an external static or

oscillating magnetic field for 15 to 30 minutes in most normal procedures, resulting in maximum gene delivery efficiency. Siene Ng W et al. subjected mouse corneal cells to an oscillating magnetic field for 30 minutes and 60 minutes, finding that the 30 minute exposure time resulted in the most efficient gene transfection. (101) Furthermore, we observed maximal cellular absorption of DNA after 30 minutes of exposure to the magnetic field in our prior research. In order to increase the cellular absorption of magnetoplexes, increasing the exposure period was shown to be ineffective. (11)

In reality, because the gene transfection duration is reduced, the short exposure duration promotes a reduction in cytotoxicity, especially when transfections are conducted in serum-free conditions. A prolonged magnetic exposure period has also been recorded in some situations. For example, Oral O et al. simultaneously treated cancer cells with different magnetic fields for 6–8 hours (98), although stem cells have seldom been exposed to such lengthy durations of magnetic exposure. The incubation duration of magnetoplexes after removing the magnetic field, on the other hand, had a significant influence on gene transport efficiency. The gene expression levels of MSCs were increased 3.18 0.60-fold when the incubation duration was increased from 4 to 20 hours after the magnetic field was removed. (22)

In general, magnetic exposure duration and magnetoplex incubation time had little effect on gene expression levels, but employing IONPs to abbreviate transfection time is preferred to reduce the dangers of transfection operations on stem cells.

4.3 Interference with Serum

Because the positively charged surface of gene vectors is simple to bond with the negatively charged serum protein, resulting in a substantial decline in gene delivery effectiveness, serum protein interference is one of the key barriers for most non-viral gene delivery systems. (102) Furthermore, these coupled serum proteins will create a protein corona on the gene complexes, resulting in unwanted interactions between the gene complexes and negatively charged cell membranes, as well as an expanded size of the gene complexes, resulting in reduced cellular uptake. (103)

Negative serum protein impacts also impact IONPs with positive surface modifications. (104) For example, when comparing positive PEI-modified magnetite nanoparticles to negative poly (acrylic acid)-modified magnetite nanoparticles, positive PEI-modified magnetite nanoparticles absorbed more proteins. (105) The surface characteristics and dispersion of magnetoplexes were modified by protein absorption, which hampered their cellular uptake. (47) As a result, most magnetofections are carried out in a serum-free medium, such as PolyMAG (Chemicell GmbH, Germany) for ESCs (17) and MSCs (22), and NeuroMag (Oz Biosciences, France) for NSCs. (18) Due to stem cells' great sensitivity to the environment, gene delivery under serum-free circumstances may raise hazards such as cytotoxicity and loss of stem cell characteristics. (106)

As a result, most recent research has focused on investigating the possibility of serum-resistant gene delivery employing an elegant shell-layer architecture on IONPs. (107) For example, we previously constructed a magnetic gene complex (MGC) that was made layer-by-layer (LBL) using SPIONs, cationic pullulan, and DNA. The negative charged DNA neutralized the partial charge of the cationic pullulan on the surface, allowing for a sufficient surface charge. Furthermore, because the DNA was bundled inside two cationic pullulan layers, this LBL fabrication shielded the transported DNA from serum interference. Furthermore, the rapid sedimentation of MGC to the cell surfaces caused by the external magnetic force reduced the formation rate of the protein corona, reducing the negative effects of serum proteins on both size and surface zeta potential, resulting in a high gene delivery efficiency in serum-contained conditions. (11)

Additionally, hastening the formation of magnetoplexes in target cells might shorten the gene transfection process, which might be another technique for reducing serum protein toxicity. After serum adsorption, Arsianti M et al. found that the negatively charged magnetoplexes still had a high amount of cellular absorption. The dominant magnetic attraction force, which pushed the magnetoplexes toward the cell membrane despite the negative surface charge, was credited with this finding. (47) Gu Z's group also tweaked the PEI to carboxylic acid-silane coated SPIONs mix ratio, resulting in a low aggregated gene complex. During a 10-minute magnetofection, this gene combination demonstrated less protein adsorption than PEI/DNA complexes, indicating serum resistant gene delivery. (108) The same group also compared two types of IONPs with similar sizes but different saturation magnetization values (50 and 33 emu g⁻¹ particles). The IONPs with higher saturation magnetization values were significantly superior to the lower ones, especially in the presence of serum, due to their faster accumulation. (109) These findings also show that IONPs with a high saturation magnetization value and a sophisticated shell-layer coating design can reduce serum adsorption while maintaining a high cellular uptake level, even when the negatively charged protein corona is present, indicating that serum-resistant gene delivery to stem cells is a viable option.

4.4 Gene Transfection Systems in Three Dimensions

Compared to two-dimensional (2D) gene transfection systems, gene delivery in 3D settings, referred to as 3D gene transfection systems, has previously been established, exhibiting advantages in terms of generating both greater and more sustained gene expression levels. (110) Culturing cells in 3D scaffolds increases the surface area of cell membranes, allowing gene complexes to make more contact with cells, resulting in higher gene expression levels. (111) Furthermore, gene complexes connected to the 3D scaffold provide a DNA pool for continuous gene delivery to cells, allowing for extended gene expression. (112)

The 3D gene transfection methods are ideal for gene delivery to stem cells, not only because of the benefits of attaining highly effective gene delivery, but also because of their ability to retain stem cells' physiological features. Several earlier investigations have shown that long-term 2D monolayer culture of MSCs changes their internal structure, negatively impacting cellular senescence, immunogenicity, stemness, and paracrine activity. (113) Culturing MSCs in 3D, on the other hand, resulted in improved anti-inflammatory capabilities and encouraged bone regeneration. (115) However, gene delivery vectors developed for monolayer cultivated cells may be inadequate for 3D cultured stem cell gene transfer. As a result, IONPs have been used to aid in the transport of 3D genes to stem cells. Zhang H et al. offered one example, finding that a variety of commercially available transfection reagents were ineffective in delivering siRNA molecules or shRNA plasmids into 3D cultivated cells, whereas IONPs were able to achieve a high gene delivery efficiency of those 3D cultivated cells (1116). Furthermore, Pickard MR et al. were the first to demonstrate that IONPs could safely transfer genes to the 3D neurosphere (NSCs). (18) They have just published a full description of their procedure for delivering effective genes to 3D-growing NSCs. (117) To summarize, these examples suggest that combining IONPs with 3D gene transfection methods might be a potential technique for increasing gene expression levels while minimizing negative effects on stem cell in vivo capabilities.

IV. OBSTACLES

We've shown that employing IONPs to improve gene transport efficiency in stem cells has huge potential and fundamental principles. However, actual applications of this potent gene delivery technique are still in the early stages of development, with significant obstacles to overcome. For example, IONP safety issues are one of the most significant roadblocks to its use with stem cells. When compared to other cell types, such as 293T cells, stem cells showed a significant sensitivity to toxicity in response to the same dosage of IONPs. (22) However, because IONP cytotoxicity is tightly tied to dose-dependent effects, (15), it may be greatly reduced by optimizing concentrations. The unique properties of stem cells, such as self-renewal, differentiation potential, and migratory ability, necessitate a lot of attention. The large-scale synthesis of IONPs with homogeneous size and shape is another common difficulty. With large-scale production, low consistency and high inter batch variability of IONPs had unfavorable effects on the physiochemical characteristics of IONPs, which hampered optimum gene transport to stem cells in practical applications.

5.1 Differentiation

The formation of iron-catalyzed reactive oxygen species (ROS) generated by IONPs or iron molecules has been shown to alter stem cell differentiation capabilities, (15), 118, which has a negative influence on stem cell therapeutic potential and raises safety concerns. However, in most studies that used IONPs with stem cells, such negative effects were rarely documented. The reasons for this are partially attributable to the fact that the number of IONPs used for gene delivery is inadequate to generate large levels of ROS. (15, 119) Liu J et al. revealed that an optimized low dose of SPIONs had no effect on the differentiation and self-renewal characteristics of ESCs in one case. (120)

Furthermore, Zare S et al. found that SPIONs at doses lower than 25 mg mL⁻¹ had no negative impact on the differentiation characteristics of dental pulp stem cells. (121) Adipogenic, osteogenic, and chondrogenic differentiation capabilities of human adipose tissue-derived stem cells were not affected by amine-surface-modified SPIONs at the same dose. (122) FIONs at appropriate concentrations did not cause excess ROS and had no negative effects on the multifunctional differentiation potential of human placenta-derived MSCs, including osteogenic, adipogenic, and chondrogenic differentiation, according to a prior study. (21) Mohanty S et al. recently showed that IONPs had no effect on the ability of human MSCs to differentiate into cardiac and brain cells. (123) IONPs had no effect on the capacity of NSCs to develop into immature neurons and astrocytes, in addition to MSCs. (124) Furthermore, maghemite nanoparticles were shown to have no effect on HiPSC-NP neural differentiation. (64) As a result, IONPs at an ideal low dose do not impact the differentiating capability of various stem cells in the majority of cases.

Kolecka MA et al. recently demonstrated that whereas SPIONs had no effect on MSC osteogenic or adipogenic development, they did impede chondrogenic development. (125) Chang YK et al. found that amine (NH₃⁺)-surface-modified SPIONs reduced MSCs' osteogenic and chondrogenic differentiation capacity but had no influence on adipogenic differentiation capacity. (126) Because of the dose-dependent reduction of osteogenic differentiation produced by SPIONs, these observed inhibitions of differentiation potential are thought to be strongly connected to the amount of IONPs employed. (127) Interestingly, IONPs stimulated osteogenic differentiation of human bone marrow-derived MSCs in vitro via activating the mitogen-activated protein kinase signal pathway, according to recent research. (128) Jiang P et al. found that bovine serum albumin-loaded IONPs improved the osteogenic differentiation of bone marrow-derived MSCs only when exposed to a continuous static magnetic field. (129)

These examples demonstrate the complex effects of IONPs on stem cell differentiation potential, which are influenced by IONP dose and physiochemical parameters, as well as the magnetic field applied. As a result, understanding the principles of how IONPs alter the differentiation capacity of stem cells remains a difficult task.

5.2 Biologic Behavior

5.2.1 Cell Migration

MSCs, NSCs, and ESCs, for example, have the potential to migrate spontaneously to diseased tissues, which is known as "homing capacity." The interaction of cytokines or chemokines released by infected tissues with their appropriate receptors on stem cells is part of stem cells' ability. (5) 132 For example, after ischemic injury, the production of chemokine-stromal-derived factor 1 (SDF-1) encourages MSC homing into the infected brain, owing to SDF-1's interaction with the chemokine receptor CXCR4 expressed on cell membranes. (133) The possible impact of IONPs on transfected stem cell migration merits special consideration for this aim. Furthermore, the use of IONPs to identify stem cells was hampered by these problems. (135)

In an early study, ferucarbotran (Resovist, Bayer Schering Pharma AG, Germany), a clinically approved SPION for liver imaging, was found to reduce the migration capacity of human MSCs when coated with Pulsin (PolyPlus Transfection), a transfection reagent. However, this negative effect was eliminated after two passages. (136) The precise biological pathways causing this effect remain unknown. Low doses (50-100 g mL⁻¹) of ferucarbotran inhibited *in vitro* migration in swine peripheral blood-derived endothelial progenitor cells, but this effect was removed at high doses (>200 g mL⁻¹). (137) Nonetheless, Chen YC et al. found that ferucarbotran promoted the migration capacity of human MSCs at a dosage of 300 g mL⁻¹, attributing the effect to ferucarbotran eliciting Fe-dependent Wnt-mediated matrix metalloproteinase 2 expression, about a year after the initial report of impaired stem cell migration induced by ferucarbotran. (127) Various iron oxide-based nanoparticles have been discovered to actively boost the homing-related chemokine receptor CXCR4 expression of bone-marrow-derived MSCs, therefore increasing the homing capabilities of MSCs in both traumatic brain injury and glioblastoma models, according to Chen X's group in 2014. They further established that this biological impact was exclusively seen with iron-based nanoparticles. The iron ions released by nanoparticles were thought to increase hypoxia-inducible factor-1 expression, which in turn increased CXCR4 expression levels. (24) Using FIONs, we were able to demonstrate this physiologic impact on human placenta-derived MSCs. (21) Li X et al. recently revealed that IONPs boosted the expression of additional migration-related proteins in bone marrow-derived MSCs, including c-Met and C-C motif chemokine receptor 1. (138) In separate research, Huang RY et al. found that MSCs that had been transfected with hyaluronic acid-decorated SPIONs had a larger number of migrating cells at tumor locations than MSCs that had not been transfected. (30) However, it appears that IONPs' potential is not uniformly applicable to all cell types. NeuroMag, for example, has no effect on the migration of rat oligodendrocyte precursor cells. (26) Furthermore, multiple previous studies (13 (39) used IONPs-based cell labeling to track the *in vivo* migration of rat NSCs and human hematopoietic progenitor cells, demonstrating that IONPs did not impair their homing ability significantly. Unfortunately, the ability of cells labeled with or without IONPs to migrate was not assessed in these investigations. To the best of our knowledge, this accelerated cell migration generated by IONPs has been more thoroughly described in MSCs. Hence, more research focused on this crucial element for other stem cell types is greatly sought.

5.2.2 Intercellular Communication

Gap junction intercellular communication (GJIC) is essential for stem cell physiological characteristics, including proliferation, apoptosis, differentiation, migration, and organogenesis, to continue. (140) Earlier research has suggested that improving gap junction development has promoted improved stem cell therapeutic effectiveness in tissue regeneration. (141) Jäderstad J et al. gave an example in which the GJIC played a significant part in the integration of exogenous NSCs into the recipient neuronal network in the brain. (142)

According to recent research, IONPs have the capacity to activate the gap junctional signaling cascade by boosting the overexpression of the gap junction protein connexin 43 (Cx43). (48, 143) After endosomal absorption, partial ionization of IONPs into free iron ions promotes c-Jun N-terminal kinases-mediated Cx43 expression, according to the biological process. (48) As a result of this theory, IONPs may have an effect on the GJIC of stem cells. However, as far as we are aware, no published literature has looked at the possible harm of IONPs to stem cells, necessitating additional research.

5.3 Synthesis at a Large Scale

Most current studies of recruiting IONPs to improve gene delivery efficiency are focusing on the precise controlled synthesis of magnetic iron oxide nanocores, as well as designed surface functional modifications to enable optimal physicochemical properties for highly efficient gene delivery to stem cells, as described above. The difficulty in maintaining the consistency of IONPs with excellent physicochemical characteristics after extending their production above the milligram-scale (144) has hampered the practical use of this IONPs-assisted gene delivery technique for stem cells. As a result, large-scale manufacturing of IONPs with the desired physicochemical features has become a problem.

Physical approaches, such as the "top-down" technique, can manufacture a huge number of nanoparticles. However, this technique is restricted due to the difficulties of maintaining homogeneity. Chemical synthesis approaches, on the other hand, demonstrate advantages in the controlled creation of uniform nanoparticles, although a lack of subgram amounts is common. (66) As a result, large-scale synthesis of nanoparticles with a restricted size range, excellent monodispersity, and homogeneous composition has been pursued. Hyeon T's group, for example, created an ultra-large-scale synthesis of monodisperse IONPs by thermal decomposition utilizing the colloidal heat-up approach, which can generate up to 40 g of nanoparticles in a single batch. (69) Furthermore, the particle size of IONPs manufactured by the heat-up approach can be adjusted by adding additives such as oleyl alcohol, resulting in very tiny IONPs (3 nm) using just 5 g per batch reaction. (54, 145) Meanwhile, Jia CJ et al. described another novel approach for the large-scale preparation of high-quality, tailor-made iron oxide nanorings, in which -Fe₂O₃ nanorings were first controllably synthesized via a hydrothermal method, and then converted to magnetite or maghemite via a reduction or reduction-

oxidation process. (146) Furthermore, a one-pot procedure based on thermal breakdown for the large-scale synthesis of IONPs was recently described, generating over 50 g in a single reaction. (147) Using a single reaction, Li Y et al. demonstrated a simple solution-based dehydration approach for ultra-large-scale synthesis of IONPs (875 g). (148) A green synthetic approach for producing IONPs with high consistency was recently described utilizing *Citrullus colocynthis* pulp and seed aqueous extract, which might be easily modified for large-scale IONP synthesis. (149) In addition to these chemical methods, bacterial fermentation has been used to produce IONPs on a massive scale. From 30 L batch fermentations employing microbial production, over 1 kg (wet weight) of Zn-substituted magnetite was recovered, and the magnetic nanoparticles produced demonstrated excellent monodispersity and a highly repeatable particle size. (150)

Furthermore, in terms of industrial-scale production, continuous flow reactors have demonstrated outstanding superiority in terms of high reproducibility when compared to the above batch reactors, but their applications are typically limited due to the broad size distribution of the produced nanoparticles. (54) As a result, a droplet flow reactor-based synthesis was recently developed, displaying a narrower size range than conventional batch synthesis and considerably greater repeatability for IONP production at an industrial scale. (151) Aside from large-scale magnetic-core preparation, large-scale IONP transfer to aqueous environments is critical for gene delivery applications. IONPs made by the heat-up process, for example, are coated with oleic acid, resulting in low water dispersibility. (69) Using a reverse-micelle-based oxidative process, Cai J et al. devised an efficient and large-scale approach for phase transfer of these IONPs to the aqueous phase. (152)

Following the historical lessons of the withdrawal of dextran-coated IONPs (Feridex, Resovist, and Ferumoxitol) from the American and European markets as MRI contrast agents, which was partially due to the broad size distribution, (14, 153), further efforts at consistent production of uniform IONPs, as well as the large-scale transfer of IONPs to the aqueous phase, deserve a lot of thought.

CONCLUSION

The recent developments in using IONPs to increase gene transport to stem cells are detailed in this review, which emphasizes the unique features of IONPs as biocompatible metal-based gene delivery vectors. The physicochemical features of IONPs have a significant influence on gene transport efficacy and biocompatibility of stem cells, as outlined in this paper. For effective and repeatable gene delivery, regulated syntheses of homogenous IONPs are preferred. Furthermore, synthesising or assembling IONPs with greater ARs can improve their cellular absorption, increasing the efficacy of gene transport to stem cells. Furthermore, magnetofection technology has had a significant impact on gene transport of stem cells. An unoptimized transfection technique resulted in considerable cytotoxicity as well as a considerable drop in gene expression levels. Gene delivery employing IONPs and external magnetic force, on the other hand, showed encouraging results in overcoming serum interference and enhancing the transport of target genes into 3D cell cultures. Notably, serum-resistant and 3D gene transfer is advantageous for maintaining stem cell survival and stemness following magnetofection.

However, significant hurdles remain in the way of IONP-assisted gene transport to stem cells, including the unknown bioeffects of IONPs on stem cell behavior and the large-scale manufacture of monodispersed IONPs with regulated size and shape. When used for gene delivery at optimal doses, IONPs have no negative impact on the viability, proliferation, and differentiation potential of stem cells. However, the dose-dependent toxicity of IONPs, as well as the possible dangers associated with the use of transfection agents such as PEI, necessitate particular caution.

Furthermore, the possible bio-influences of IONPs and ionized ions on stem cell biologic behaviors should be carefully explored, and research into additional undiscovered bioeffects should continue. Meanwhile, another problem worth considering for the actual usage of IONPs as a potent and ubiquitous platform tool to deliver target genes to stem cells for medical purposes is the large-scale synthesis of homogenous IONPs with minimal interbatch differences.

In summary, IONPs have demonstrated their exceptional potential for increasing the efficacy of gene delivery to stem cells, which, combined with their excellent biocompatibility and promising functionality, makes them superior to other gene delivery methods in terms of multifunctional stem cell engineering. However, the challenges of using IONPs for gene delivery to stem cells, which involve chemistry, physics, material science, pharmaceuticals, and cell biology, necessitate more multidisciplinary collaborations in order to achieve breakthroughs and translate this promising stem cell gene delivery strategy into medical practice (154-218).

REFERENCES

1. E. Fuchs, T. Tumber, G. Guasch, *Cell* 2004, 116, 769;
2. b) J. M. Gimble, A. J. Katz, B. A. Bunnell, *Circ. Res.* 2007, 100, 1249;
3. c) C. E. Murry, G. Keller, *Cell* 2008, 132, 661;
4. d) P. Dharmasaroja, *J Clin Neurosci* 2009, 16, 12;
5. e) H. Wang, P. Agarwal, Y. Xiao, H. Peng, S. Zhao, X. Liu, S. Zhou, J. Li, Z. Liu, X. He, *ACS Cent. Sci.* 2017, 3, 875;
6. f) H. Mizuno, M. Tobita, A. C. Uysal, *STEM CELLS* 2012, 30, 804.
7. 2H. Sakata, K. Niizuma, H. Yoshioka, G. S. Kim, J. E. Jung, M. Katsu, P. Narasimhan, C. M. Maier, Y. Nishiyama, P. H. Chan, *J. Neurosci.* 2012, 32, 3462.

8. 3X. C. Jiang, J. J. Xiang, H. H. Wu, T. Y. Zhang, D. P. Zhang, Q. H. Xu, X. L. Huang, X. L. Kong, J. H. Sun, Y. L. Hu, K. Li, Y. Tabata, Y. Q. Shen, J. Q. Gao, *Adv. Mater.* 2019, 31, 1807591.
9. 4L. Liu, S. X. Zhang, W. Liao, H. P. Farhoodi, C. W. Wong, C. C. Chen, A. I. Segaliny, J. V. Chacko, L. P. Nguyen, M. Lu, G. Polovin, E. J. Pone, T. L. Downing, D. A. Lawson, M. A. Digman, W. Zhao, *Sci. Transl. Med.* 2017, 9, ean2966.
10. 5a) Y. L. Hu, Y. H. Fu, Y. Tabata, J. Q. Gao, *J. Controlled Release* 2010, 147, 154;
11. b) B. Huang, Y. Tabata, J. Q. Gao, *J. Controlled Release* 2012, 162, 464.
12. 6a) T. Y. Zhang, B. Huang, H. B. Wu, J. H. Wu, L. M. Li, Y. X. Li, Y. L. Hu, M. Han, Y. Q. Shen, Y. Tabata, J. Q. Gao, *J. Controlled Release* 2015, 209, 260;
13. b) T. Y. Zhang, B. Huang, Z. Y. Yuan, Y. L. Hu, Y. Tabata, J. Q. Gao, *Nanomed: Nanotechnol, Biol. Med* 2014, 10, 257.
14. 7a) W. Walther, U. Stein, *Drugs* 2000, 60, 249;
15. b) S. Hacein-Bey-Abina, C. von Kalle, M. Schmidt, F. Le Deist, N. Wulffraat, E. McIntyre, I. Radford, J. L. Villeval, C. C. Fraser, M. Cavazzana-Calvo, A. Fischer, *N. Engl. J. Med.* 2003, 348, 255;
16. c) D. W. Pack, A. S. Hoffman, S. Pun, P. S. Stayton, *Nat. Rev. Drug Discovery* 2005, 4, 581;
17. d) M. A. Kay, J. C. Glorioso, L. Naldini, *Nat. Med.* 2001, 7, 33;
18. e) D. Luo, W. M. Saltzman, *Nat. Biotechnol.* 2000, 18, 33.
19. 8X. Y. Bak, J. Yang, S. Wang, *Cancer Gene Ther.* 2010, 17, 721.
20. 9E. Zhao, Z. Zhao, J. Wang, C. Yang, C. Chen, L. Gao, Q. Feng, W. Hou, M. Gao, Q. Zhang, *Nanoscale* 2012, 4, 5102.
21. 10a) S. Guo, Y. Huang, Q. Jiang, Y. Sun, L. Deng, Z. Liang, Q. Du, J. Xing, Y. Zhao, P. C. Wang, A. Dong, X. J. Liang, *ACS Nano* 2010, 4, 5505;
22. b) W. J. Song, J. Z. Du, T. M. Sun, P. Z. Zhang, J. Wang, *Small* 2010, 6, 239;
23. c) X. Huang, Y. F. Lai, G. B. Braun, N. O. Reich, *Small* 2017, 13, 1602473.

24. 11a) T. Y. Zhang, J. H. Wu, Q. H. Xu, X. R. Wang, J. Lu, Y. Hu, J. I. Jo, M. Yamamoto, D. Ling, Y. Tabata, J. Q. Gao, *Int. J. Pharm.* 2017, 520, 1;
25. b) Q. Xu, T. Zhang, Q. Wang, X. Jiang, A. Li, Y. Li, T. Huang, F. Li, Y. Hu, D. Ling, J. Gao, *Int. J. Pharm.* 2018, 552, 443;
26. c) B. Shah, P. T. Yin, S. Ghoshal, K. B. Lee, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* 2013, 52, 6190.
27. 12a) J. Jung, A. Solanki, K. A. Memoli, K. Kamei, H. Kim, M. A. Drahl, L. J. Williams, H. R. Tseng, K. Lee, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* 2010, 49, 103;
28. b) Y. Li, X. Duan, L. Jing, C. Yang, R. Qiao, M. Gao, *Biomaterials* 2011, 32, 1923;
29. c) H. Y. Tian, J. Chen, X. S. Chen, *Small* 2013, 9, 2034.
30. 13S. Rana, A. Bajaj, R. Mout, V. M. Rotello, *Adv. Drug Delivery Rev.* 2012, 64, 200.
31. 14a) D. Ling, T. Hyeon, *Small* 2013, 9, 1450;
32. b) D. Ling, N. Lee, T. Hyeon, *Acc. Chem. Res.* 2015, 48, 1276.
33. 15a) C. Plank, O. Zelphati, O. Mykhaylyk, *Adv. Drug Delivery Rev.* 2011, 63, 1300;
34. b) G. Liu, J. Gao, H. Ai, X. Chen, *Small* 2013, 9, 1533;
35. c) E. Delyagina, W. Li, N. Ma, G. Steinhoff, *Nanomedicine* 2011, 6, 1593;
36. d) D. A. Dean, D. D. Strong, W. E. Zimmer, *Gene Ther.* 2005, 12, 881.
37. 16a) C. Plank, F. Scherer, U. Schillinger, M. Anton, *J Gene Med* 2000, 2, 24;
38. b) F. Scherer, M. Anton, U. Schillinger, J. Henke, C. Bergemann, A. Kruger, B. Gansbacher, C. Plank, *Gene. Ther.* 2002, 9, 102;
39. c) C. Mah, T. J. Fraithe Jr., I. Zolotukhin, S. Song, T. R. Flotte, J. Dobson, C. Batich, B. J. Byrne, *Mol. Ther.* 2002, 6, 106.
40. 17a) C. H. Lee, E. Y. Kim, K. Jeon, J. C. Tae, K. S. Lee, Y. O. Kim, M. Y. Jeong, C. W. Yun, D. K. Jeong, S. K. Cho, J. H. Kim, H. Y. Lee, K. Z. Riu, S. G. Cho, S. P. Park, *Stem Cells Dev.* 2008, 17, 133;
41. b) H. C. Wu, T. W. Wang, M. C. Bohn, F. H. Lin, M. Spector, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* 2010, 20, 67.
42. 18a) M. R. Pickard, P. Barraud, D. M. Chari, *Biomaterials* 2011, 32, 2274;
43. b) C. F. Adams, M. R. Pickard, D. M. Chari, *Nanomedicine: Nanotechnol, Biol. Med.* 2013, 9, 737.
44. 19a) O. Mykhaylyk, Y. Sanchez-Antequera, D. Vlaskou, E. Hammerschmid, M. Anton, O. Zelphati, C. Plank, *Methods Mol. Biol.* 2010, 605, 487;
45. b) O. Mykhaylyk, O. Zelphati, E. Hammerschmid, M. Anton, J. Rosenecker, C. Plank, *Methods Mol. Biol.* 2009, 487, 111.
46. 20Y. Ma, Z. Zhang, X. Wang, W. Xia, H. Gu, *Int. J. Pharm.* 2011, 419, 247.
47. 21T. Y. Zhang, F. Y. Li, Q. H. Xu, Q. Y. Wang, X. C. Jiang, Z. Y. Liang, H. W. Liao, X. L. Kong, J. A. Liu, H. H. Wu, D. P. Zhang, C. H. An, L. Dong, Y. Lu, H. C. Cao, D. Kim, J. H. Sun, T. Hyeon, J. Q. Gao, D. S. Ling, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* 2019, 29, 1900603.
48. 22a) S. Son, M. S. Liang, P. Lei, X. Xue, E. P. Furlani, S. T. Andreadis, *Bioconjugate Chem.* 2015, 26, 1314;
49. b) S. J. Park, K. Na, *Biomaterials* 2012, 33, 6485;
50. c) S. Brunner, T. Sauer, S. Carotta, M. Cotten, M. Saltik, E. Wagner, *Gene. Ther.* 2000, 7, 401.
51. 23L. Ferreira, J. M. Karp, L. Nobre, R. Langer, *Cell Stem Cell* 2008, 3, 136.
52. 24X. Huang, F. Zhang, Y. Wang, X. Sun, K. Y. Choi, D. Liu, J. S. Choi, T. H. Shin, J. Cheon, G. Niu, X. Chen, *ACS Nano* 2014, 8, 4403.

53. 25A. R. Fernandes, D. M. Chari, *J. Controlled Release* 2016, 238, 289.
54. 26S. I. Jenkins, M. R. Pickard, N. Granger, D. M. Chari, *ACS Nano* 2011, 5, 6527.
55. 27M. A. Yamoah, M. Moshref, J. Sharma, W. C. Chen, H. A. Ledford, J. H. Lee, K. S. Chavez, W. Wang, J. E. Lopez, D. K. Lieu, P. Sirish, X. D. Zhang, *Int. J. Nanomed.* 2018, 13, 6073.
56. 28S. Albukhaty, H. Naderi-Manesh, T. Tiraihi, *Iran Biomed J.* 2013, 17, 71.
57. 29W. Park, H. N. Yang, D. Ling, H. Yim, K. S. Kim, T. Hyeon, K. Na, K. H. Park, *Biomaterials* 2014, 35, 7239.
58. 30R. Y. Huang, Y. H. Lin, S. Y. Lin, Y. N. Li, C. S. Chiang, C. W. Chang, *Theranostics* 2019, 9, 2411.
59. 31J. W. Park, S. H. Ku, H. H. Moon, M. Lee, D. Choi, J. Yang, Y. M. Huh, J. H. Jeong, T. G. Park, H. Mok, S. H. Kim, *Macromol. Biosci.* 2014, 14, 380.
60. 32G. J. Delcroix, M. Jacquart, L. Lemaire, L. Sindji, F. Franconi, J. J. Le Jeune, C. N. Montero-Menei, *Brain Res.* 2009, 1255, 18.
61. 33N. Gandra, D. D. Wang, Y. Zhu, C. Mao, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* 2013, 52, 11278.
62. 34M. Magro, T. Martinello, E. Bonaiuto, C. Gomiero, D. Baratella, G. Zoppellaro, G. Cozza, M. Patruno, R. Zboril, F. Vianello, *Biochim. Biophys. Acta, Gen. Subj.* 2017, 1861, 2802.
63. 35J. S. Park, W. Park, S. J. Park, A. C. Larson, D. H. Kim, K. H. Park, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* 2017, 27, 1700396.
64. 36B. Cao, P. Qiu, C. Mao, *Microscopy Res Technique* 2013, 76, 936.
65. 37a) M. Barrow, A. Taylor, P. Murray, M. J. Rosseinsky, D. J. Adams, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 2015, 44, 6733;
66. b) Q. Wang, X. Ma, H. Liao, Z. Liang, F. Li, J. Tian, D. Ling, *ACS Nano* 2020, 14, 2053.
67. 38a) M. Zhu, G. Nie, H. Meng, T. Xia, A. Nel, Y. Zhao, *Acc. Chem. Res.* 2013, 46, 622;
68. b) X. Duan, Y. Li, *Small* 2013, 9, 1521.
69. 39a) S. Tenzer, D. Docter, J. Kuharev, A. Musyanovych, V. Fetz, R. Hecht, F. Schlenk, D. Fischer, K. Kiouptsi, C. Reinhardt, K. Landfester, H. Schild, M. Maskos, S. K. Knauer, R. H. Stauber, *Nat. Nanotechnol.* 2013, 8, 772;
70. b) J. Sun, Y. Xianyu, M. Li, W. Liu, L. Zhang, D. Liu, C. Liu, G. Hu, X. Jiang, *Nanoscale* 2013, 5, 5262;
71. c) H. Dong, H. S. Parekh, Z. P. Xu, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* 2015, 437, 10;
72. d) K. Nambara, K. Niikura, H. Mitomo, T. Ninomiya, C. Takeuchi, J. Wei, Y. Matsuo, K. Ijiri, *Langmuir* 2016, 32, 12559;
73. e) E. A. Sykes, Q. Dai, C. D. Sarsons, J. Chen, J. V. Rocheleau, D. M. Hwang, G. Zheng, D. T. Cramb, K. D. Rinker, W. C. Chan, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 2016, 113, E1142.
74. 40a) W. K. Ko, D. N. Heo, H. J. Moon, S. J. Lee, M. S. Bae, J. B. Lee, I. C. Sun, H. B. Jeon, H. K. Park, I. K. Kwon, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* 2015, 438, 68;
75. b) J. Zhu, L. Liao, L. Zhu, P. Zhang, K. Guo, J. Kong, C. Ji, B. Liu, *Talanta* 2013, 107, 408;
76. c) A. Xu, M. Yao, G. Xu, J. Ying, W. Ma, B. Li, Y. Jin, *Int. J. Nanomedicine* 2012, 7, 3547.
77. 41J. Huang, L. Bu, J. Xie, K. Chen, Z. Cheng, X. Li, X. Chen, *ACS Nano* 2010, 4, 7151.
78. 42T. L. Moore, L. Rodriguez-Lorenzo, V. Hirsch, S. Balog, D. Urban, C. Jud, B. Rothen-Rutishauser, M. Lattuada, A. Petri-Fink, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 2015, 44, 6287.
79. 43Y. Liu, B. Workalemahu, X. Jiang, *Small* 2017, 13, 1701815.
80. 44B. D. Chithrani, W. C. Chan, *Nano Lett.* 2007, 7, 1542.
81. 45a) J. Jo, I. Aoki, Y. Tabata, *J. Controlled Release* 2010, 142, 465;
82. b) L. H. Reddy, J. L. Arias, J. Nicolas, P. Couvreur, *Chem. Rev.* 2012, 112, 5818.
83. 46A. H. Lu, E. L. Salabas, F. Schuth, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* 2007, 46, 1222.
84. 47M. Arsianti, M. Lim, C. P. Marquis, R. Amal, *Langmuir* 2010, 26, 7314.
85. 48J. Han, B. Kim, J. Y. Shin, S. Ryu, M. Noh, J. Woo, J. S. Park, Y. Lee, N. Lee, T. Hyeon, D. Choi, B. S. Kim, *ACS Nano* 2015, 9, 2805.
86. 49a) P. Zhang, B. Li, J. Du, Y. Wang, *Colloids Surf., B* 2017, 157, 18;
87. b) X. Huang, X. Teng, D. Chen, F. Tang, J. He, *Biomaterials* 2010, 31, 438.
88. 50R. Agarwal, V. Singh, P. Journey, L. Shi, S. V. Sreenivasan, K. Roy, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 2013, 110, 17247.
89. 51P. Yan, R. Wang, N. Zhao, H. Zhao, D. F. Chen, F. J. Xu, *Nanoscale* 2015, 7, 5281.
90. 52S. Dasgupta, T. Auth, G. Gompper, *Nano Lett.* 2014, 14, 687.
91. 53H. Herd, N. Daum, A. T. Jones, H. Huwer, H. Ghandehari, C. M. Lehr, *ACS Nano* 2013, 7, 1961.
92. 54a) R. Chalasani, S. Vasudevan, *J. Phys. Chem. C* 2011, 115, 18088;
93. b) H. J. Kwon, K. Shin, M. Soh, H. Chang, J. Kim, J. Lee, G. Ko, B. H. Kim, D. Kim, T. Hyeon, *Adv. Mater.* 2018, 30, 1704290.
94. 55M. Li, X. Li, X. Qi, F. Luo, G. He, *Langmuir* 2015, 31, 5190.
95. 56L. Yang, Z. Wang, L. Ma, A. Li, J. Xin, R. Wei, H. Lin, R. Wang, Z. Chen, J. Gao, *ACS Nano* 2018, 12, 4605.
96. 57M. Rabel, P. Warncke, C. Gruttner, C. Bergemann, H. D. Kurland, R. Muller, V. Dugandzic, J. Thamm, F. A. Muller, J. Popp, D. Cialla-May, D. Fischer, *Nanomedicine* 2019, 14, 1681.
97. 58a) N. A. Frey, S. Peng, K. Cheng, S. Sun, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 2009, 38, 2532;
98. b) O. Veisoh, J. W. Gunn, M. Zhang, *Adv. Drug Delivery Rev.* 2010, 62, 284;
99. c) R. Namgung, K. Singha, M. K. Yu, S. Jon, Y. S. Kim, Y. Ahn, I. K. Park, W. J. Kim, *Biomaterials* 2010, 31, 4204;

- 100.d) H. P. Song, J. Y. Yang, S. L. Lo, Y. Wang, W. M. Fan, X. S. Tang, J. M. Xue, S. Wang, *Biomaterials* 2010, 31, 769;
- 101.e) M. Barrow, A. Taylor, A. M. Fuentes-Caparros, J. Sharkey, L. M. Daniels, P. Mandal, B. K. Park, P. Murray, M. J. Rosseinsky, D. J. Adams, *Biomater. Sci.* 2017, 6, 101;
- 102.f) M. Ahmadzadeh, C. Romero, J. McCloy, *AIP Adv.* 2018, 8, 056807.
- 103.59E. J. Park, H. N. Umh, D. H. Choi, M. H. Cho, W. Choi, S. W. Kim, Y. Kim, J. H. Kim, *Arch. Toxicol.* 2014, 88, 1607.
- 104.60N. Singh, G. J. Jenkins, R. Asadi, S. H. Doak, *Nano Reviews* 2010, 1, 5358.
- 105.61a) J. Skopalik, K. Polakova, M. Havrdova, I. Justan, M. Magro, D. Milde, L. Knopfova, J. Smarda, H. Polakova, E. Gabrielova, F. Vianello, J. Michalek, R. Zboril, *Int. J. Nanomed.* 2014, 9, 5355;
- 106.b) V. Cmiel, J. Skopalik, K. Polakova, J. Solar, M. Havrdova, D. Milde, I. Justan, M. Magro, Z. Starcuk, I. Provaznik, *Eur. Biophys. J.* 2017, 46, 433.
- 107.62a) J. T. Jang, H. Nah, J. H. Lee, S. H. Moon, M. G. Kim, J. Cheon, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* 2009, 48, 1234;
- 108.b) C. Barcena, A. K. Sra, G. S. Chaubey, C. Khemtong, J. P. Liu, J. Gao, *Chem. Commun.* 2008, 2224.
- 109.63a) V. Herynek, K. Turnovcova, A. Galisova, O. Kaman, D. Marekova, J. Koktan, M. Vosmanska, L. Kosinova, P. Jendelova, *ChemistryOpen* 2019, 8, 155;
- 110.b) B. Novotna, K. Turnovcova, P. Veverka, P. Rossner Jr., Y. Bagryantseva, V. Herynek, P. Zvatora, M. Vosmanska, M. Klementova, E. Sykova, P. Jendelova, *Nanotoxicology* 2016, 10, 662.
- 111.64K. Jirakova, M. Seneklova, D. Jirak, K. Turnovcova, M. Vosmanska, M. Babic, D. Horak, P. Veverka, P. Jendelova, *Int. J. Nanomed.* 2016, 11, 6267.
- 112.65a) I. M. Adjei, B. Sharma, V. Labhasetwar, *Adv Exp Med Biol* 2014, 811, 73;
- 113.b) N. Lee, D. Yoo, D. Ling, M. H. Cho, T. Hyeon, J. Cheon, *Chem. Rev.* 2015, 115, 10637.
- 114.66J. Park, J. Joo, S. G. Kwon, Y. Jang, T. Hyeon, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* 2007, 46, 4630.
- 115.67A. Kunzmann, B. Andersson, C. Vogt, N. Feliu, F. Ye, S. Gabrielsson, M. S. Toprak, T. Buerki-Thurnherr, S. Laurent, M. Vahter, H. Krug, M. Muhammed, A. Scheynius, B. Fadeel, *Toxicol. Appl. Pharmacol.* 2011, 253, 81.
- 116.68a) T. Hyeon, S. S. Lee, J. Park, Y. Chung, H. B. Na, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 2001, 123, 12798;
- 117.b) N. Lee, H. Kim, S. H. Choi, M. Park, D. Kim, H. C. Kim, Y. Choi, S. Lin, B. H. Kim, H. S. Jung, H. Kim, K. S. Park, W. K. Moon, T. Hyeon, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 2011, 108, 2662.
- 118.69a) J. Park, K. An, Y. Hwang, J. G. Park, H. J. Noh, J. Y. Kim, J. H. Park, N. M. Hwang, T. Hyeon, *Nat. Mater.* 2004, 3, 891;
- 119.b) S. Sun, H. Zeng, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 2002, 124, 8204.
- 120.70H. Itoh, T. Sugimoto, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* 2003, 265, 283.
- 121.71F. H. Chen, Q. Gao, G. Y. Hong, J. Z. Ni, *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.* 2008, 320, 1775.
- 122.72S. Laurent, D. Forge, M. Port, A. Roch, C. Robic, L. Vander Elst, R. N. Muller, *Chem. Rev.* 2008, 108, 2064.
- 123.73a) K. Pombo Garcia, K. Zarschler, L. Barbaro, J. A. Barreto, W. O'Malley, L. Spiccia, H. Stephan, B. Graham, *Small* 2014, 10, 2516;
- 124.b) A. Verma, F. Stellacci, *Small* 2010, 6, 12.
- 125.74Y. J. Wang, T. Quercy-Jouvet, H. H. Wang, A. W. Li, C. P. Chak, S. Xuan, L. Shi, D. F. Wang, S. F. Lee, P. C. Leung, C. B. S. Lau, K. P. Fung, K. C. Leung, *Materials* 2011, 4, 703.
- 126.75X. M. Zhu, Y. X. Wang, K. C. Leung, S. F. Lee, F. Zhao, D. W. Wang, J. M. Lai, C. Wan, C. H. Cheng, A. T. Ahuja, *Int. J. Nanomedicine* 2012, 7, 953.
- 127.76C. Zhang, B. Wangler, B. Morgenstern, H. Zentgraf, M. Eisenhut, H. Untenecker, R. Kruger, R. Huss, C. Seliger, W. Semmler, F. Kiessling, *Langmuir* 2007, 23, 1427.
- 128.77B. Chertok, A. E. David, V. C. Yang, *Biomaterials* 2010, 31, 6317.
- 129.78D. L. Thorek, A. Tsourkas, *Biomaterials* 2008, 29, 3583.
- 130.79a) C. H. Choi, L. Hao, S. P. Narayan, E. Auyeung, C. A. Mirkin, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 2013, 110, 7625;
- 131.b) E. Frohlich, *Int. J. Nanomed.* 2012, 7, 5577.
- 132.80a) B. Zhou, L. Zheng, C. Peng, D. Li, J. Li, S. Wen, M. Shen, G. Zhang, X. Shi, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 2014, 6, 17190;
- 133.b) S. Hobel, A. Loos, D. Appelhans, S. Schwarz, J. Seidel, B. Voit, A. Aigner, *J. Controlled Release* 2011, 149, 146;
- 134.c) S. T. Haque, E. H. Chowdhury, *Curr. Drug Delivery* 2018, 15, 485.
- 135.81A. Remy-Kristensen, J. P. Clamme, C. Vuilleumier, J. G. Kuhry, Y. Mely, *Biochim. Biophys. Acta, Biomembr.* 2001, 1514, 21.
- 136.82O. Mykhaylyk, Y. S. Antequera, D. Vlaskou, C. Plank, *Nat. Protoc.* 2007, 2, 2391.
- 137.83T. H. Chung, S. C. Hsu, S. H. Wu, J. K. Hsiao, C. P. Lin, M. Yao, D. M. Huang, *Nanoscale* 2018, 10, 2998.
- 138.84Z. Sohrabijam, M. Saeidifar, A. Zamanian, *Colloids Surf., B.* 2017, 152, 169.
- 139.85J. H. Hwang, S. Lee, E. Kim, J. S. Kim, C. H. Lee, I. S. Ahn, J. H. Jang, *Int. J. Pharm.* 2011, 421, 397.
- 140.86E. Boisselier, D. Astruc, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 2009, 38, 1759.
- 141.87a) S. Wang, K. J. Chen, T. H. Wu, H. Wang, W. Y. Lin, M. Ohashi, P. Y. Chiou, H. R. Tseng, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* 2010, 49, 3777;
- 142.b) Y. Jin, C. Jia, S. W. Huang, M. O'Donnell, X. Gao, *Nat. Commun.* 2010, 1, 41.
- 143.88C. Xu, J. Xie, D. Ho, C. Wang, N. Kohler, E. G. Walsh, J. R. Morgan, Y. E. Chin, S. Sun, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* 2008, 47, 173.

- 144.89J. E. Lee, N. Lee, T. Kim, J. Kim, T. Hyeon, *Acc. Chem. Res.* 2011, 44, 893.
- 145.90O. Mykhaylyk, T. Sobisch, I. Almstatter, Y. Sanchez-Antequera, S. Brandt, M. Anton, M. Dobliger, D. Eberbeck, M. Settles, R. Braren, D. Lerche, C. Plank, *Pharm. Res.* 2012, 29, 1344.
- 146.91a) K. Niikura, T. Matsunaga, T. Suzuki, S. Kobayashi, H. Yamaguchi, Y. Orba, A. Kawaguchi, H. Hasegawa, K. Kajino, T. Ninomiya, K. Ijio, H. Sawa, *ACS Nano* 2013, 7, 3926;
- 147.b) S. Kralj, D. Makovec, *ACS Nano* 2015, 9, 9700.
- 148.92R. Wang, Y. Hu, N. Zhao, F. J. Xu, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 2016, 8, 11298.
- 149.93M. Arsianti, M. Lim, C. P. Marquis, R. Amal, *Biomacromolecules* 2010, 11, 2521.
- 150.94S. Emmrich, W. Wang, K. John, W. Li, B. M. Putzer, *Molecular Cancer* 2009, 8, 61.
- 151.95a) S. C. McBain, U. Griesenbach, S. Xenariou, A. Keramane, C. D. Batich, E. W. Alton, J. Dobson, *Nanotechnology* 2008, 19, 405102;
- 152.b) Q. A. Pankhurst, J. Connolly, S. K. Jones, J. Dobson, *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.* 2003, 36, R167.
- 153.96S. W. Kamau, P. O. Hassa, B. Steitz, A. Petri-Fink, H. Hofmann, M. Hofmann-Antenbrink, B. von Rechenberg, M. O. Hottiger, *Nucleic. Acids. Res.* 2006, 34, e40.
- 154.97S. W. K. Chapman, P. O. Hassa, S. Koch-Schneidemann, B. von Rechenberg, M. Hofmann-Antenbrink, B. Steitz, A. Petri-Fink, H. Hofmann, M. O. Hottiger, *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.* 2008, 320, 1517.
- 155.98O. Oral, T. Cikim, M. Zuvun, O. Unal, H. Yagci-Acar, D. Gozuacik, A. Kosar, *Ann. Biomed. Eng.* 2015, 43, 2816.
- 156.99a) J. Dobson, *Nat. Nanotechnol.* 2008, 3, 139;
- 157.b) J. H. Lee, E. S. Kim, M. H. Cho, M. Son, S. I. Yeon, J. S. Shin, J. Cheon, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* 2010, 49, 5698.
- 158.100L. J. Lu, Y. Wang, F. Zhang, M. W. Chen, B. L. Lin, X. H. Duan, M. H. Cao, C. S. Zheng, J. J. Mao, X. T. Shuai, J. Shen, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* 2018, 28, 1706769.
- 159.101W. Siene Ng, K. Binley, B. Song, J. E. Morgan, *Lancet* 2015, 385, S75.
- 160.102H. M. Wu, S. R. Pan, M. W. Chen, Y. Wu, C. Wang, Y. T. Wen, X. Zeng, C. B. Wu, *Biomaterials* 2011, 32, 1619.
- 161.103A. L. Capriotti, G. Caracciolo, G. Caruso, P. Foglia, D. Pozzi, R. Samperi, A. Lagana, *Anal. Biochem.* 2011, 419, 180.
- 162.104a) J. Ashby, S. Pan, W. Zhong, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 2014, 6, 15412;
- 163.b) V. Hirsch, C. Kinnear, M. Moniatte, B. Rothen-Rutishauser, M. J. Clift, A. Fink, *Nanoscale* 2013, 5, 3723.
- 164.105M. P. Calatayud, B. Sanz, V. Raffa, C. Riggio, M. R. Ibarra, G. F. Goya, *Biomaterials* 2014, 35, 6389.
- 165.106a) K. Ettayebi, S. E. Crawford, K. Murakami, J. R. Broughman, U. Karandikar, V. R. Tenge, F. H. Neill, S. E. Blutt, X. L. Zeng, L. Qu, B. Kou, A. R. Opekun, D. Burrin, D. Y. Graham, S. Ramani, R. L. Atmar, M. K. Estes, *Science* 2016, 353, 1387;
- 166.b) E. V. Alakpa, V. Jayawarna, A. Lampel, K. V. Burgess, C. C. West, S. C. J. Bakker, S. Roy, N. Javid, S. Fleming, D. A. Lamprou, J. L. Yang, A. Miller, A. J. Urquhart, P. W. J. M. Frederix, N. T. Hunt, B. Peault, R. V. Ulijn, M. J. Dalby, *Chem.* 2016, 1, 298;
- 167.c) W. Wagner, A. D. Ho, *Stem Cell Rev.* 2007, 3, 239.
- 168.107U. Sakulkhu, M. Mahmoudi, L. Maurizi, G. Coullerez, M. Hofmann-Antenbrink, M. Vries, M. Motazacker, F. Rezaee, H. Hofmann, *Biomater. Sci.* 2015, 3, 265.
- 169.108L. Xie, Q. Jiang, Y. He, Y. Nie, D. Yue, Z. Gu, *Biomater. Sci.* 2015, 3, 446.
- 170.109L. Xie, W. Jiang, Y. Nie, Y. Y. He, Q. Jiang, F. Lan, Y. Wu, Z. W. Gu, *RSC Adv.* 2013, 3, 23571.
- 171.110C. X. He, N. Li, Y. L. Hu, X. M. Zhu, H. J. Li, M. Han, P. H. Miao, Z. J. Hu, G. Wang, W. Q. Liang, Y. Tabata, J. Q. Gao, *Pharm. Res.* 2011, 28, 1577.
- 172.111J. H. Jang, L. D. Shea, *J. Controlled Release* 2003, 86, 157.
- 173.112H. Storrie, D. J. Mooney, *Adv. Drug Delivery Rev.* 2006, 58, 500.
- 174.113a) S. Morikawa, Y. Mabuchi, Y. Kubota, Y. Nagai, K. Niibe, E. Hiratsu, S. Suzuki, C. Miyauchi-Hara, N. Nagoshi, T. Sunabori, S. Shimmura, A. Miyawaki, T. Nakagawa, T. Suda, H. Okano, Y. Matsuzaki, *J. Exp. Med.* 2009, 206, 2483;
- 175.b) C. Toma, W. R. Wagner, S. Bowry, A. Schwartz, F. Villanueva, *Circ. Res.* 2009, 104, 398;
- 176.c) Y. Qiao, Z. Xu, Y. Yu, S. Hou, J. Geng, T. Xiao, Y. Liang, Q. Dong, Y. Mei, B. Wang, H. Qiao, J. Dai, G. Suo, *Biomaterials* 2020, 227, 119573;
- 177.d) M. W. Laschke, M. D. Menger, *Trends Biotechnol.* 2017, 35, 133.
- 178.114T. J. Bartosh, J. H. Ylostalo, A. Mohammadipoor, N. Bazhanov, K. Coble, K. Claypool, R. H. Lee, H. Choi, D. J. Prockop, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 2010, 107, 13724.
- 179.115A. Chatterjea, V. L. LaPointe, A. Barradas, H. Garritsen, H. Yuan, A. Renard, C. A. van Blitterswijk, J. de Beor, *Eur. Cells Mater.* 2017, 33, 121.
- 180.116H. Zhang, M. Y. Lee, M. G. Hogg, J. S. Dordick, S. T. Sharfstein, *ACS Nano* 2010, 4, 4733.
- 181.117M. R. Pickard, C. F. Adams, D. M. Chari, *Current Protocols Stem Cell Biol.* 2017, 40, 2D.19.1.
- 182.118V. I. Shubayev, T. R. Pisanic 2nd, S. Jin, *Adv. Drug Delivery Rev.* 2009, 61, 467.
- 183.119R. M. Patil, N. D. Thorat, P. B. Shete, P. A. Bedge, S. Gavde, M. G. Joshi, S. A. M. Tofail, R. A. Bohara, *Biochem Biophys Rep.* 2018, 13, 63.
- 184.120J. Liu, L. Wang, J. Cao, Y. Huang, Y. Lin, X. Wu, Z. Wang, F. Zhang, X. Xu, G. Liu, *Nanoscale* 2014, 6, 9025.

- 185.121S. Zare, D. Mehrabani, R. Jalli, M. Saeedi Moghadam, N. Manafi, G. Mehrabani, I. Jamhiri, S. Ahadian, *J. Clin. Med.* 2019, 8, 1418.
- 186.122N. Wang, J. Y. Zhao, X. Guan, Y. Dong, Y. Liu, X. Zhou, R. Wu, Y. Du, L. Zhao, W. Zou, C. Han, L. Song, B. Sun, Y. Liu, J. Liu, *Cell Biol. Int.* 2015, 39, 899.
- 187.123S. Mohanty, K. G. Jain, S. B. Nandy, A. Kakkar, M. Kumar, A. K. Dinda, H. Singh, A. Ray, *Mol. Cell. Biochem.* 2018, 448, 17.
- 188.124R. L. Azevedo-Pereira, B. Rangel, F. Tovar-Moll, E. L. Gasparetto, M. Attias, C. Zaverucha-do-Valle, Jasmin, R. Mendez-Otero, *Mol. Biol. Rep.* 2019, 46, 191.
- 189.125A. S. Arbab, G. T. Yocum, H. Kalish, E. K. Jordan, S. A. Anderson, A. Y. Khakoo, E. J. Read, J. A. Frank, *Blood* 2004, 104, 1217.
- 190.126Y. K. Chang, Y. P. Liu, J. H. Ho, S. C. Hsu, O. K. Lee, *J. Orthopaed Res.* 2012, 30, 1499.
- 191.127a) J. Fan, Y. Tan, L. Jie, X. Wu, R. Yu, M. Zhang, *Stem Cell Research & Therapy* 2013, 4, 44;
- 192.b) Y. C. Chen, J. K. Hsiao, H. M. Liu, I. Y. Lai, M. Yao, S. C. Hsu, B. S. Ko, Y. C. Chen, C. S. Yang, D. M. Huang, *Toxicol. Appl. Pharmacol.* 2010, 245, 272.
- 193.128Q. Wang, B. Chen, M. Cao, J. Sun, H. Wu, P. Zhao, J. Xing, Y. Yang, X. Zhang, M. Ji, N. Gu, *Biomaterials* 2016, 86, 11.
- 194.129P. Jiang, Y. Zhang, C. Zhu, W. Zhang, Z. Mao, C. Gao, *Acta Biomater.* 2016, 46, 141.
- 195.130C. W. Lu, J. K. Hsiao, H. M. Liu, C. H. Wu, *Sci. Rep.* 2017, 7, 3587.
- 196.131A. Balakumaran, E. Pawelczyk, J. Ren, B. Sworder, A. Chaudhry, M. Sabatino, D. Stroncek, J. A. Frank, P. G. Robey, *PLoS One* 2010, 5, e11462.
- 197.132H. H. Wu, Y. Zhou, Y. Tabata, J. Q. Gao, *J. Controlled Release* 2019, 294, 102.
- 198.133a) A. Peled, I. Petit, O. Kollet, M. Magid, T. Ponomaryov, T. Byk, A. Nagler, H. Ben-Hur, A. Many, L. Shultz, O. Lider, R. Alon, D. Zipori, T. Lapidot, *Science* 1999, 283, 845;
- 199.b) X. Cui, J. Chen, A. Zacharek, Y. Li, C. Roberts, A. Kapke, S. Savant-Bhonsale, M. Chopp, *Stem Cells* 2007, 25, 2777.
- 200.134a) Y. L. Hu, B. Huang, T. Y. Zhang, P. H. Miao, G. P. Tang, Y. Tabata, J. Q. Gao, *Mol. Pharmaceutics* 2012, 9, 2698;
- 201.b) Y. L. Hu, P. H. Miao, B. Huang, T. Y. Zhang, Z. J. Hu, Y. Tabata, J. Q. Gao, *J. Biomed. Nanotechnol.* 2014, 10, 299;
- 202.c) B. Huang, X. C. Jiang, T. Y. Zhang, Y. L. Hu, Y. Tabata, Z. Chen, S. Pluchino, J. Q. Gao, *Int. J. Pharm.* 2017, 531, 90.
- 203.135S. J. Kim, B. Lewis, M. S. Steiner, U. V. Bissa, C. Dose, J. A. Frank, *Contrast Media Mol. Imaging* 2016, 11, 55.
- 204.136R. Schafer, R. Kehlbach, M. Muller, R. Bantleon, T. Kluba, M. Ayturan, G. Siegel, H. Wolburg, H. Northoff, K. Dietz, C. D. Claussen, J. Wiskirchen, *Cytotherapy* 2009, 11, 68.
- 205.137J. X. Yang, W. L. Tang, X. X. Wang, *Cytotherapy* 2010, 12, 251.
- 206.138X. Li, Z. Wei, H. Lv, L. Wu, Y. Cui, H. Yao, J. Li, H. Zhang, B. Yang, J. Jiang, *Int. J. Nanomed.* 2019, 14, 573.
- 207.139a) W. Z. Zhu, X. Li, J. P. Qi, Z. P. Tang, W. Wang, L. Wei, H. Lei, *Biomed. Environ. Sci.* 2008, 21, 420;
- 208.b) H. E. Daldrup-Link, M. Rudelius, G. Piontek, S. Metz, R. Brauer, G. Debus, C. Corot, J. Schlegel, T. M. Link, C. Peschel, E. J. Rummeny, R. A. J. Oostendorp, *Radiology* 2005, 234, 197.
- 209.140a) B. Parekkadan, Y. Berdichevsky, D. Irimia, A. Leeder, G. Yarmush, M. Toner, J. B. Levine, M. L. Yarmush, *Neurosci. Lett.* 2008, 438, 190;
- 210.b) P. W. Dyce, D. Li, K. J. Barr, G. M. Kidder, *Stem Cells Dev.* 2014, 23, 1636.
- 211.141a) J. Y. Hahn, H. J. Cho, H. J. Kang, T. S. Kim, M. H. Kim, J. H. Chung, J. W. Bae, B. H. Oh, Y. B. Park, H. S. Kim, *J. Am. College Cardiol* 2008, 51, 933;
- 212.b) J. P. Connell, E. Augustini, K. J. Moise Jr., A. Johnson, J. G. Jacot, *J. Cell. Mol. Med.* 2013, 17, 774.
- 213.142J. Jaderstad, L. M. Jaderstad, J. Li, S. Chintawar, C. Salto, M. Pandolfo, V. Ourednik, Y. D. Teng, R. L. Sidman, E. Arenas, E. Y. Snyder, E. Herlenius, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 2010, 107, 5184.
- 214.143Y. C. Mou, S. H. Lv, F. Xiong, Y. Han, Y. W. Zhao, J. J. Li, N. Gu, J. Zhou, *J. Biomed. Mater. Res., Part B* 2018, 106, 121.
- 215.144N. Desai, *AAPS J.* 2012, 14, 282.
- 216.145B. H. Kim, N. Lee, H. Kim, K. An, Y. I. Park, Y. Choi, K. Shin, Y. Lee, S. G. Kwon, H. B. Na, J. G. Park, T. Y. Ahn, Y. W. Kim, W. K. Moon, S. H. Choi, T. Hyeon, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 2011, 133, 12624.
- 217.146C. J. Jia, L. D. Sun, F. Luo, X. D. Han, L. J. Heyderman, Z. G. Yan, C. H. Yan, K. Zheng, Z. Zhang, M. Takano, N. Hayashi, M. Eltschka, M. Klau, U. Rudiger, T. Kasama, L. Cervera-Gontard, R. E. Dunin-Borkowski, G. Tzvetkov, J. Raabe, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 2008, 130, 16968.
- 218.147L. Wang, D. Su, L. Zeng, N. Liu, L. Jiang, X. Feng, K. G. Neoh, E. T. Kang, *Dalton Trans.* 2013, 42, 13642.
- 219.148Y. Z. Li, F. Y. Ma, X. T. Su, L. J. Shi, B. B. Pan, Z. G. Sun, Y. L. Hou, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 2014, 53, 6718.
- 220.149F. Farouk, M. Abdelmageed, M. Azam Ansari, H. M. E. Azzazy, *Biotechnol. Lett.* 2020, 42, 231.
- 221.150J. W. Moon, C. J. Rawn, A. J. Rondinone, L. J. Love, Y. Roh, S. M. Everett, R. J. Lauf, T. J. Phelps, *J. Ind. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* 2010, 37, 1023.
- 222.151a) C. D. Ahrberg, J. W. Choi, B. G. Chung, *Beilstein J. Nanotechnol.* 2018, 9, 2413;
- 223.b) K. Kumar, A. M. Nightingale, S. H. Krishnadasan, N. Kamaly, M. Wylenzinska-Arridge, K. Zeissler, W. R. Branford, E. Ware, A. J. deMello, J. C. deMello, *J. Mater. Chem.* 2012, 22, 4704.

- 224.152J. Cai, Y. Q. Miao, B. Z. Yu, P. Ma, L. Li, H. M. Fan, *Langmuir* 2017, 33, 1662.
- 225.153C. Li, *Nat. Mater.* 2014, 13, 110.
- 226.154.Moataz Dowaidar, Hani Nasser Abdelhamid, Ülo Langel. Improvement of transfection with PepFects using organic and inorganic materials. 2022, *Cell Penetrating Peptides*.
- 227.155. Tomas Venit, Moataz Dowaidar , Maxime Gestin , Syed Raza Mahmood, Ülo Langel , Piergiorgio Percipalle. Transcriptional profiling reveals ribosome biogenesis, microtubule dynamics and expression of specific LncRNAs to be part of a common response to cell penetrating peptides. *Biomolecules*, 10(11), pp. 1-21, 1567, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.3390/biom10111567>.
- 228.156. HN Abdelhamid, Moataz Dowaidar, Ü Langel. Carbonized chitosan encapsulated hierarchical porous zeolitic imidazolate frameworks nanoparticles for gene delivery. *Microporous and Mesoporous Materials*, 110200, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micromeso.2020.110200>.
- 229.157. HN Abdelhamid, Moataz Dowaidar, M Hällbrink, Ü Langel. Gene Delivery Using Cell Penetrating Peptides-Zeolitic Imidazolate Frameworks. *Microporous and Mesoporous Materials*, 2020, 110173, ISSN 1387-1811, DOI:10.1016/j.micromeso.2020.110173.
- 230.158. HN Abdelhamid, Moataz Dowaidar, M Hällbrink, Ü Langel. Cell Penetrating PeptidesHierarchical Porous Zeolitic Imidazolate Frameworks Nanoparticles: An Efficient Gene Delivery Platform. Available at SSRN 3435895, 2019.
- 231.159. Moataz Dowaidar. (2018). Chimeric gene delivery vectors : Design, synthesis, and mechanisms from transcriptomics analysis (Department of Biochemistry and Biophysics, Stockholm University). <https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/record.jsf?pid=diva2:1242000>
- 232.160. Moataz Dowaidar, Hani Nasser Abdelhamid, Mattias Hällbrink, Ülo Langel, Xiaodong Zou: Chitosan enhances gene delivery of oligonucleotide complexes with magnetic nanoparticles–cell-penetrating peptide. *Journal of Biomaterials Applications* 09/2018; 33(3):392-401., DOI:10.1177/0885328218796623
- 233.161. Moataz Dowaidar, Hani Nasser Abdelhamid, Mattias Hällbrink, Krista Freimann, Kaido Kurrikoff, Xiaodong Zou, Ülo Langel: Magnetic Nanoparticle Assisted Self-assembly of Cell Penetrating Peptides-Oligonucleotides Complexes for Gene Delivery. *Scientific Reports* 08/2017; 7(1), DOI:10.1038/s41598-017-09803-z
- 234.162. Moataz Dowaidar, Hani Nasser Abdelhamid, Mattias Hällbrink, Xiaodong Zou, Ülo Langel: Graphene oxide nanosheets in complex with cell penetrating peptides for oligonucleotides delivery. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA) - General Subjects* 07/2017; 1861(9), DOI:10.1016/j.bbagen.2017.07.002
- 235.163. Moataz Dowaidar, Jakob Regberg, Dimitar A. Dobchev, Tõnis Lehto, Mattias Hällbrink, Mati Karelson, Ülo Langel: Refinement of a Quantitative Structure–Activity Relationship Model for Prediction of Cell-Penetrating Peptide Based Transfection Systems. *International Journal of Peptide Research and Therapeutics* 07/2016; 23(1), DOI:10.1007/s10989-016-9542-8
- 236.164. Maxime Gestin, Moataz Dowaidar, Ülo Langel: Uptake Mechanism of Cell-Penetrating Peptides. *Peptides and Peptide-based Biomaterials and their Biomedical Applications*, 10/2017: pages 255-264; ISBN: 978-3-319-66094-3, DOI:10.1007/978-3-319-66095-0_11
- 237.165. Ahmed A.A. Ali, Nahla M. Wassim, Moataz M. Dowaidar, Ahmed E. Yaseen: Genetic polymorphism of CYP2D6 gene among Egyptian hypertensive cases. *The Journal of Basic & Applied Zoology*, 08/2013; 66(4), 228-233. DOI:10.1016/j.jobaz.2012.12.002
- 238.166. Ahmed A.A. Ali, Nahla M. Wassim, Moataz Dowaidar, Ahmed E. Yaseen: Association of eNOS (E298D) and CYP2J2 (-50 G/T) gene polymorphisms with hypertension among Egyptian cases. *The Journal of Basic & Applied Zoology*, 08/2013; 66(4), 234-241. DOI:10.1016/j.jobaz.2012.12.001
- 239.167. Almeman Ahmad, Khalaf Hassan, Rasool Semaab, Moataz Dowaidar, Al Orainy Mohammad: The impact of CYP2C19 polymorphism on platelet reactivity for guiding clopidogrel treatment and cost analysis. *Journal of the Saudi Heart Association* 04/2013; 25(2):107., DOI:10.1016/j.jsha.2013.03.005
- 240.168. Abdullah Algasham, Hisham Ismail, Moataz Dowaidar, Ahmad A Settin: Methylenetetrahydrofolate Reductase (MTHFR) and Angiotensin Converting Enzyme (ACE) Gene Polymorphisms among Saudi Population from Qassim Region. 01/2013; 5(2 Suppl 1):3-4. PMC3533339
- 241.169. Abdullah Alghasham, Ahmad A Settin, Ahmad Ali, Moataz Dowaidar, Hisham Ismail: Association of MTHFR C677T and A1298C gene polymorphisms with hypertension. 12/2012; 6(1):3-11., DOI:10.12816/0005968
- 242.170. Ahmad Ali, Abdullah Alghasham, Hisham Ismail, Moataz Dowaidar, Ahmad Settin: ACE I/D and eNOS E298D gene polymorphisms in Saudi subjects with hypertension. *Journal of Renin-AngiotensinAldosterone System* 10/2012; 14(4), DOI:10.1177/1470320312459976
- 243.171. Abdullah Alghasham, Ahmad Ali, Hisham Ismail, Moataz Dowaidar, Ahmad A Settin: CYP2J2-50 G/T and ADRB2 G46A gene polymorphisms in saudi subjects with hypertension. *Genetic Testing and Molecular Biomarkers* 06/2012; 16(9):1027-31., DOI:10.1089/gtmb.2012.0006
- 244.172. Ahmad A Settin, Abdullah Alghasham, Ahmad Ali, Moataz Dowaidar, Hisham Ismail: Frequency of thrombophilic genetic polymorphisms among Saudi subjects compared with other populations. *Hematology (Amsterdam, Netherlands)* 05/2012; 17(3):176-82., DOI:10.1179/102453312X13376952196575

- 245.173. HA Ismail, AA Alghasham, MM Dowaidar, AA Settin: Polymorphisms in MTHF and ace genes and the association with hypertension among Saudi population from Qassim region. 06/2011; 29(1)., DOI:10.4314/ejbmb.v29i1.67382
- 246.174. Badr Aljarallah, Ahmed Ali, Moataz Dowaidar, Ahmad Settin: Prevalence of α -1-Antitrypsin Gene Mutations in Saudi Arabia. Saudi Journal of Gastroenterology 03/2011; 17(4):256-60., DOI:10.4103/1319-3767.82580
- 247.175. Moataz Dowaidar, Ahmad Settin: Risk of Myocardial Infarction Related to Factor V Leiden Mutation: A Meta-Analysis. Genetic Testing and Molecular Biomarkers 08/2010; 14(4):493-8., DOI:10.1089/gtmb.2010.0017
- 248.176. Ahmad A Settin, Abdullah Algasham, Moataz Dowaidar, Hisham Ismail: Methylene Tetrahydrofolate Reductase and Angiotensin Converting Enzyme Gene Polymorphisms Related to Overweight/Obesity among Saudi Subjects from Qassim Region. Disease markers 11/2009; 27(2):97-102., DOI:10.3233/DMA-2009-0660
- 249.177. Ahmad Settin, Hala Almarsafawy, Ahmad Alhussieny, Moataz Dowaidar: Dysmorphic Features, Consanguinity and Cytogenetic Pattern of Congenital Heart Diseases: a pilot study from Mansoura Locality, Egypt. 07/2008; 2(2):101-11. PMC3068729
- 250.178. Ahmad Settin, Moataz Dowaidar, Rizk El-Baz, Ayman Abd-Al-Samad, Ibrahim El-Sayed, Mahmoud Nasr: Frequency of factor V Leiden mutation in Egyptian cases with myocardial infarction. Hematology (Amsterdam, Netherlands) 07/2008; 13(3):170-4., DOI:10.1179/102453308X316158
- 251.179. Ahmad Settin, Ibrahim S Abu-Saif, Rizk El-Baz, Moataz Dowaidar, Rabab Abu-Al Kasim, Shaimaa Shabana: Diagnosis of Sex Chromosome Disorders and Prenatal Diagnosis of Down Syndrome using Interphase Fluorescent In-Situ Hybridization Technique. 07/2007; 1(2):203-9. PMID: 21475429 PMC: PMC3068641
- 252.180. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021. "Metabolic Syndrome_ the Presence of Inflammatory Mechanisms in Abdominal Obesity Is Undeniable, Gene Therapy Using Nanoparticles and Adenoviruses Technologies Is Promising." OSF Preprints. April 5. doi:10.31219/osf.io/2j5xt.
- 253.181. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021. "Nanomedicine Has Elegantly Attempted to Cure Multiple Gene Polymorphisms and Mutations in Cardiovascular Diseases Using Gene Therapy Techniques." OSF Preprints. April 5. doi:10.31219/osf.io/d3x8g.
- 254.182. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021. "Exosomes Can Make the Use of Circulating Mirna as a Biomarker More Feasible. The Aim of Gene Therapy Should Be to Learn Everything There Is to Know About Mirna Activity." OSF Preprints. April 6. doi:10.31219/osf.io/edkua.
- 255.183. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021. "Key Genetic Factors in the Metabolic Syndrome Predisposition Which May Be a Therapeutic Options by Gene Therapy." OSF Preprints. April 11. doi:10.31219/osf.io/f38sk.
- 256.184. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021. "Anti-sense Pathways Have Been Generated Using Sirna. The Liver and Other Often Used Organs Will Now Be Targeted." OSF Preprints. April 11. doi:10.31219/osf.io/m6xvp.
- 257.185. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021. "Discoveries in Gene-environment Interactions That Influence CVD, Lipid Traits, Obesity, Diabetes, and Hypertension Appear to Be Able to Influence Gene Therapy." OSF Preprints. April 11. doi:10.31219/osf.io/cr5af.
- 258.186. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021. "Genome Editing's Potential Target Diseases in the Cardiovascular Field." OSF Preprints. April 11. doi:10.31219/osf.io/gc23p.
- 259.187. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021. "The Cardiometabolic-based Chronic Disease Model Lays the Foundations for Accurate, Evidence-based Preventive Targeting and Gene Therapy." OSF Preprints. April 11. doi:10.31219/osf.io/up9z4.
- 260.188. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021. "Researchers Would Be Able to Develop a Detailed Picture of Chromatin in Disease, Which Would Be Useful for Gene Therapy." OSF Preprints. April 11. doi:10.31219/osf.io/m9z48.
- 261.189. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021. "Mirna Can Be a Part of Both the Onset and Cure of Coronary Heart Disease." OSF Preprints. April 11. doi:10.31219/osf.io/teqh8.
- 262.190. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021. "Crispr/cris Systems Are Highly Effective and Useful for Genomic Manipulation. Despite This, Cardiac Treatment Remains Difficult Due to Existing Genome Editing and Delivery Processes." OSF Preprints. April 11. doi:10.31219/osf.io/3nwzd.
- 263.191. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021. "Metabolic Syndrome_ the Presence of Inflammatory Mechanisms in Abdominal Obesity Is Undeniable, Gene Therapy Using Nanoparticles and Adenoviruses Technologies Is Promising." OSF Preprints. April 5. doi:10.31219/osf.io/2j5xt.
- 264.192. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021. "Nanomedicine Has Elegantly Attempted to Cure Multiple Gene Polymorphisms and Mutations in Cardiovascular Diseases Using Gene Therapy Techniques." OSF Preprints. April 5. doi:10.31219/osf.io/d3x8g.
- 265.193. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021. "Exosomes Can Make the Use of Circulating Mirna as a Biomarker More Feasible. The Aim of Gene Therapy Should Be to Learn Everything There Is to Know About Mirna Activity." OSF Preprints. April 6. doi:10.31219/osf.io/edkua.
- 266.194. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021. "Key Genetic Factors in the Metabolic Syndrome Predisposition Which May Be a Therapeutic Options by Gene Therapy." OSF Preprints. April 11. doi:10.31219/osf.io/f38sk.
- 267.195. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021. "Anti-sense Pathways Have Been Generated Using Sirna. The Liver and Other Often Used Organs Will Now Be Targeted." OSF Preprints. April 11. doi:10.31219/osf.io/m6xvp.
- 268.196. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021. "Discoveries in Gene-environment Interactions That Influence CVD, Lipid Traits, Obesity, Diabetes, and Hypertension Appear to Be Able to Influence Gene Therapy." OSF Preprints. April 11. doi:10.31219/osf.io/cr5af.
- 269.197. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021. "Genome Editing's Potential Target Diseases in the Cardiovascular Field." OSF Preprints. April 11.

- doi:10.31219/osf.io/gc23p.
- 270.198. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021. "The Cardiometabolic-based Chronic Disease Model Lays the Foundations for Accurate, Evidence-based Preventive Targeting and Gene Therapy." OSF Preprints. April 11. doi:10.31219/osf.io/up9z4.
- 271.199. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021. "Researchers Would Be Able to Develop a Detailed Picture of Chromatin in Disease, Which Would Be Useful for Gene Therapy." OSF Preprints. April 11. doi:10.31219/osf.io/m9z48.
- 272.200. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021. "Mirna Can Be a Part of Both the Onset and Cure of Coronary Heart Disease." OSF Preprints. April 11. doi:10.31219/osf.io/teqh8.
- 273.201. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021. "Crispr/cris Systems Are Highly Effective and Useful for Genomic Manipulation. Despite This, Cardiac Treatment Remains Difficult Due to Existing Genome Editing and Delivery Processes." OSF Preprints. April 11. doi:10.31219/osf.io/3nwzd.
- 274.202. Moataz Dowaidar. 2023. Genome editing's potential target diseases in the cardiovascular field with potential influence on the ophthalmological pressure. 2023. Biogecko. DOI: <http://biogecko.co.nz/.2023.v12.i03.pp1262-1272>
- 275.203. Moataz Dowaidar. (2023). Gene-free Viral-like particles (VLPs) offer a safer alternative to inactivating or weakening viral strains for traditional vaccines. *Journal of Biomedical Engineering*, 40(2), 164–201. Retrieved from <http://www.swyxcx.cn/index.php/jbme/article/view/127>
- 276.204. Moataz Dowaidar. (2023). Exosomes can make the use of circulating miRNA as a biomarker more feasible. *Journal of Biomedical Engineering*, 40(2), 144–163. Retrieved from <http://www.swyxcx.cn/index.php/jbme/article/view/126>
- 277.205. Moataz Dowaidar. (2023). Biogenic particles can be multiantigenic, immunostimulative and activate innate immunity while suppressing tumor development. *Journal of Biomedical Engineering*, 40(2), 111–143. Retrieved from <http://www.swyxcx.cn/index.php/jbme/article/view/125>
- 278.206. Moataz Dowaidar. (2023). Genome-wide association studies (GWAS) have revolutionized our view of human health and disease genetics and offered novel gene therapy targets. *Journal of clinical otorhinolaryngology, head, and neck surgery*.
- 279.207. Moataz Dowaidar. (2023). Graphene based nanocomplexes can be rationally modified with a variety of functional compounds to improve therapeutic effectiveness including gene therapy. *Journal of clinical otorhinolaryngology, head, and neck surgery*.
- 280.208. Moataz Dowaidar. (2023). Microrobotic swarms and their robotic delivery applications offer new venues for gene therapy delivery. *Journal of clinical otorhinolaryngology, head, and neck surgery*.
- 281.209. Moataz Dowaidar. (2023). Nanomedicine potential for endometriosis treatment. *Latin American Journal of Pharmacy*.
- 282.210. Moataz Dowaidar. (2023). Human corneal endothelial cells grafts to replace cadaveric donor corneas. *Latin American Journal of Pharmacy*.
- 283.211. Moataz Dowaidar. (2023). Nanodiamond as a drug delivery vehicle and gene therapy tool. *Latin American Journal of Pharmacy*.
- 284.212. Moataz Dowaidar. (2022). Nano-powered nanobots could be useful in gene therapy delivery. *NeuroQuantology*.
- 285.213. Moataz Dowaidar. (2022). Biocompetent nanorobots can transfer chemical energy into mechanical work even in ionic environments. *NeuroQuantology*.
- 286.214. Moataz Dowaidar. (2022). Electrospun nanofibers provide a good platform to treat chronic wounds like diabetic foot ulcers. *NeuroQuantology*.
- 287.215. Moataz Dowaidar. (2022). Magnetic iron oxide nanoparticles have potential on gene therapy effectiveness and biocompatibility.
- 288.216. Moataz Dowaidar. (2022). Polydopamine may be easily functionalized with a range of nanomaterials for synergistic cancer therapy, in addition to its exceptional photothermal effects.
- 289.217. Moataz Dowaidar. (2022). Metabolic syndrome: the presence of inflammatory mechanisms in abdominal obesity is undeniable, gene therapy using nanoparticles and adenoviruses technologies is promising.
- 290.218. Moataz Dowaidar. (2022). Nanomedicine has elegantly attempted to cure multiple gene polymorphisms and mutations in cardiovascular diseases using gene therapy techniques.